

UNIVERSITAT POMPEU FABRA

MASTER THESIS

**Music remixing using source separation
to improve cochlear implant users music
perception.**

Author:

JORDI PONS

Supervisors:

W. NOGUEIRA and J. JANER

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Abstract

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by JORDI PONS

Music appreciation remains rather poor for many Cochlear Implant (CI) users due to their poor pitch perception. Simple music structures with a clear rhythm/beat are well perceived for CI users. A previous publication which studies the mixing preferences of CI users on vocal western music, shows a significant preference for higher vocals and attenuated background instruments. By re-mixing the music they are able to simplify the signal to make it more suitable for implantees. But the multitrack recordings necessary to generate a re-mix are not always accessible; only mono/stereo pre-mixed audio files are available. In order to overcome this limitation, we propose to use current Source Separation (SS) state-of-the-art techniques to estimate the multitrack recordings. The perceptual studies conducted are focused on studying how the errors/artifacts produced by a SS algorithm, Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF), affect the music mixing preferences. These show that when attenuating the background instruments by 6dB, the artifacts/errors present in the vocals are not perceived by CI users. Then, SS can be used to estimate the multitrack.

To our knowledge, no previous work exist on trying to simplify classical music for CI users by means of re-mixing. This work shows the influence of the music genre on CI users mixing preferences. We show that CI users with classical musical training have a significant preference for mixing pre-sets that enforce musicological details difficult to encode with CIs (others than beat). However, CI users without classical music training do not show any significant preference, probably due to the lack of music understanding.

This work also shows how CI users may not benefit from general mixing pre-sets solutions. Technologies like SS, that allow individual configurations, seem to be the right approach towards a better music appreciation.

Additionally, we studied a new approach for source signal separation based on deep recurrent neural networks (DRNN). Recently, some researchers successfully used DRNN for singing voice separation from monaural recordings in a supervised setting. A great advantage of this technique, compared to NMF, is that allows similar performance reducing the processing time; which is crucial for CI applications. In this work, we investigated how different theoretically motivated initialization schemes behave when training DRNN for SS. Concluding that if the initialization allows the output activations to be inside the data range, the model is able to find a good local minimum. It is also introduced a theoretically motivated interpretation of why music models (considering neighbouring frames as input vector) do not suffer the gradient vanish/explode problem.

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Abbreviations

CI	Cochlear Implant
NH	Normal Hearing
SS	Source Separation
MT	Multi-Track
NMF	Non-negative Matrix Factorization
FASST	Flexible Audio Source Separation Toolbox
NN	Neural Network
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DRNN	Deep Recurrent Neural Network
HPSS	Harmonic Percussive Sound Separation
PSA	Prior Subspace Analysis

Chapter 1

Introduction

This section presents the main hypothesis and research questions. The research topic and the reasons that motivate the proposed approach are introduced. Ultimately the followed strategy and the work plan are exposed.

1.1 Motivation and goals

A way to bring back the hearing sense to people with hearing impairment is to provide them assistive listening devices; two kinds are available nowadays: hearing aids and cochlear implants. Hearing aids are electroacoustic devices that are designed to amplify and equalize sounds. Basically, they work outside the auditory system as earplugs that amplify and correct the impaired hearing measured by an audiometry. But not all users can benefit of hearing aids; for instance: people with severe to profound hearing loss. For those people (assuming that they have a functioning auditory nerve) it exists another possibility: cochlear implants (CIs). CIs are surgically implanted electronic devices that provide sense of sound to a person who is profoundly deaf. It is conformed by two parts: external (microphone, sound processor and transmitter) and internal (receiver and electrodes). The external part processes the sound to be transmitted to the implanted internal part of the device that is responsible of sending stimulus to the auditory nerve by means of the electrodes situated inside the cochlea.

Both devices are historically more focused on trying to improve the hearing experience of speech sounds (to bring back to users the capacity of communicating). Their performance is still far away to allow people with hearing impairment to perceive speech equal to normal-hearing people, they just work well under a good listening environment (no background noise or with limited echo) [Moore, 2003]. But the characteristics of the music signal are different from speech. For many people using CIs music is currently hard to perceive. This work focuses on improving CI users musical experience.

Many researchers studied that field reaching many interesting conclusions (extensively explained in Section 2.1), from where is hypothesized:

- CIs have an important lack of frequency resolution (using 16-22 spectral channels). What is enough for speech intelligibility and rhythm perception [Buyens et al., 2014], but not for melody recognition: that requires complex pitch perception (strongly dependent on the spectral cues) [Galvin et al., 2009]. Simpler music signals (in the sense that fewer instruments are present in the audio mix) are preferred for implantees [Buyens et al., 2014; Gfeller et al., 2003].

CI-Hypothesis 1: CI users would listen better if the music is simplified emphasizing the audio sources that the device can transmit better: singing voice and/or rhythm.

Previous literature supports this starting point [Gfeller et al., 2003; Galvin et al., 2009; Looi et al., 2008]. Specially, a pilot test carried out by Buyens et al. [2014] where they try to find the music mixing preferences of CI users. They show that re-mixing a multitrack song (*i.e.* attenuating tracks with instruments difficult to encode by the CI) for simplifying the music signal is a good strategy to improve CI users musical experience.

But normally multitrack recordings are not available; commercial songs are mixed in mono or stereo audio files. For being able to re-mix such songs, a pre-processing step for estimating the multitrack recording from the commercial mix is needed. Buyens et al. [2013] show some preliminary results on separating sounds automatically from a commercial mix for the same purpose with encouraging results.

This master thesis wants to contribute on the automatic estimation of the multitrack recording taking advantage of the state-of-the-art Source Separation (SS) techniques.

The technique proposed by [Buyens et al. \[2013\]](#) is sub-optimal (see Chapter 2) and object based SS techniques should be more appropriate.

The main goal of this master thesis consists on assess if the artifacts and errors produced by the SS algorithm are perceived by CI users.

Two different kinds of music signals are going to be considered in that study: orchestral classical music and vocal western popular music. No previous literature exist for orchestral music simplification for improving CI users music experience. This work gives the first steps towards improving classical music perception. Since it is still not demonstrated that remixing orchestral music would benefit CI users music perception, the study is carried out with multitrack recordings (no SS involved).

Is difficult to say that this approach will totally solve the problem, because the limitations of the devices will still exist; but is clear that emphasizing the enjoyable parts of the signal, will help implantees to experience music in a more pleasant way [[Buyens et al., 2014](#)]. Existing related patents by the industry leaders show the interest in this particular approach [[Buyens, 2011](#); [Fitz, 2013](#); [Strahl and Falch, 2014](#)].

1.2 Methodology

Two main research questions arise from the posed hypothesis:

- Do CI users perceive the error/artifacts produced by the non-perfect estimation of the multitrack? (using state of the art SS techniques over popular music)
- Do CI users enjoy better orchestral music given a different mixing setup than NH listeners?

To estimate the multitrack recording, the FASST framework [[Ozerov et al., 2012](#)] (for pop music) is going to be used as baseline algorithm. This state of the art algorithm is available online and will guarantee that all the experiments can be carried out. Additionally, a new powerful method for SS based on Deep Learning [[Huang et al., 2014a](#)] is also going to be considered. That topic is going to be the main research area of the signal processing part. This new technique showed to be useful for singing voice separation [[Huang et al., 2014a](#)], overcoming the current state of the art. Moreover, once

the neural networks are trained they become a high-performance low-latency algorithm; what's really interesting for assistive listening devices where real time is a must.

Those research questions will be answered considering data gathered from several perceptual studies done with CI and NH (Normal Hearing) participants. Experiment design and further details can be found in Chapter 4.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is organized in five chapters. Second chapter reviews the main concepts and the state of the art of CI users music perception and SS. Third chapter shows the implementation details of the SS algorithms. The perceptual evaluation process is explained in the fourth chapter with the description of the procedure and results. Last chapter concludes and points out future work.

Chapter 2

State of the art

Throughout this section the main concepts around CIs and its limitations for music perception are presented. The reasoning for approaching the problem by means of simplifying the music (remixing the output of a SS algorithm) are given, as well. The SS technologies used in that work are also introduced and discussed.

2.1 Cochlear Implants

Not all hearing impaired people can be implanted, only patients suffering profound hearing loss with an auditory nerve capable to transmit electric impulses to the auditory path are candidates. In most cases hearing loss is caused by damaged inner hair cells that are not able to stimulate electrically the auditory nerve. CIs function is to replace part of the auditory system responsible of stimulating the auditory nerve, sending directly small currents (in the order of μA) to the auditory nerve fibers [Hidalgo, 2012; Nogueira et al., 2005, 2009].

FIGURE 2.1: *Wearing a CI: external (left) and internal (right). The description for each of the numbers depicted in the figure, is listed below. From: [Nogueira, 2008].*

Current CIs are composed by two parts:

- External part: it is composed by the microphone (1) and the signal processor (2) in charge of filtering and correcting the gain of the different bands of the signal captured by the microphone; and the transmitter coil (4) responsible to send the processed information to the receiver coil (5). Both, (2) and (4) connected through a cable (3).
- Internal part: it is surgically implanted. It is composed by an inner receiver coil with a decoder (5) capable to obtain the information sent from the transmitter coil (4) through the skin; and an electrode array (6), inserted in the scala tympani of the cochlea, that transmits the electric impulses to the brain path (7).

For further information see: [Nogueira \[2008\]](#); [Louizou \[1999\]](#); [Moore \[2003\]](#).

Those devices are mainly designed to transmit speech, when CI convey music signals the performance is rather bad. Due to that reason, seems that CIs would perform better when listening the lyrics of a song; but if in daily situations recipient's do not perceive properly speech due to hard environmental circumstances (such as reverberation, eco or background noise), one can not expect a CI user to perform well when tracking the lyrics of a song. In that context: if the accompaniment is simpler and the songs are known, the lyrics recognition task seems easier. Some researchers suggest that following the lyrics on a CD or record jacket while listening, helps to enjoy better the music [[Gfeller et al., 2003](#)].

An important aspect that affects CI recipient's musical experience is the lack of frequency resolution. For a correct speech perception 16–22 spectral channels at the electrode array are sufficient, but for music: more than 32 channels are needed [[Galvin et al., 2009](#)]. For melody appreciation it is important the sense of pitch, what becomes hard under those low resolution constraints. Pitch can be perceived by means of temporal repetition, cochlear location and by the harmonics of a fundamental frequency (f_0). Temporal pitch perception is severely limited in CIs, that receive temporal pitch in a similar way as normal hearing (NH) listeners when all spectral cues are removed [[Burns and Viemeister, 1981](#)]. CI recipient's also can detect pitch as a function of the electrode location in the cochlea, considering the tonotopic organization of it. But the low number of channels in the electrode array and the lack of channel selectivity in the electric stimuli, converts

such mechanism to a timbral cue rather than a pitch cue. The most important aspect for musical pitch perception is provided by the harmonics of a fundamental frequency, and is still unclear what biological mechanism is responsible for harmonic pitch perception in NH listeners [Moore, 2003]. Again, CIs do not provide sufficient resolution to support harmonic pitch.

Many researchers [Kong et al., 2004; McDermott, 2004; Looi et al., 2008] agree on saying that CI listeners perceive beat and rhythm as well as NH. The low frequency parts of the signal are well encoded in the electrical stimuli of the CIs. As this low frequency parts are well transmitted, music with clear rhythm/beat structures are preferred for CI. In Gfeller et al. [2010] and Buyens et al. [2014] it is shown that simplifying the signal favoring the rhythm and the beat enhances CI musical experience. This video¹ shows a simulation on how CI users perceive speech and music; it should be helpful for the reader to listen the video to understand the problem and why the rhythm and the beat are so important.

But not all CI recipients perceive music in the same way, most of the studies show that the performance is highly variable between implantees [Galvin et al., 2009; Gfeller et al., 2003; Buyens et al., 2014]. Those differences could be determined by many factors. First, biological factors: not all the cochleas are equal, and the electrodes can not be inserted precisely in the same place. Additionally, it could exist a mismatch between the frequency of the CI's filter and the corresponding characteristic frequency in the cochlea due to surgical imprecisions. Second, the performance depends on the level of residual hearing [Looi et al., 2008]. Third, CI users have different experience wearing the implant and varying musical background that could be helpful to fill missing information.

CI are still far from being able to provide a perfect perception of music [Nogueira et al., 2011]. The CI listener should adapt himself to a new way of listening music. Training helps to get used to that new situation, the brain is able to learn how to listen under those new conditions. Rehearsal with simple and familiar songs helps to improve performance [Gfeller et al., 2003].

Given the previously described limitations on CI music perception, this work proposes to simplify the music signal automatically. Complexity reduction seems the appropriate way of approaching the musical perception problem since multiple instruments present

¹<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SpKKYBkJ9Hw>

in a mix are less pleasant than music played by a single instrument [Gfeller et al., 2010; Looi et al., 2007] and pitch recognition for CI recipients is hard in a polyphonic scenario, where the multiple pitches are fused in a single-pitch unit [Donnelly et al., 2009]. This thesis can be seen as a continuation of the work of Buyens et al. [2014], where it is shown that modifying the relative instrument level settings potentially improves popular music enjoyment for CI users. They rated different pre-set mixes of multitrack recordings, concluding that CIs prefer an audio mix with clear vocals and attenuated instruments; where the more salient instruments are the bass and the drum, responsible of rhythm and beat.

But multitrack recordings are not always available, most commercial releases are mono or stereo mixes. In the previous literature only appears one attempt, by Buyens et al. [2013], for trying to reduce complexity automatically over real-world signals (that are mainly monophonic or stereo, not multitrack). The simplification of the music is done:

1. Estimating the multitrack recording from a commercial mix with an algorithm called *Harmonic/Percussive Sound Separation* (HPSS).
2. Simplifying the music attenuating the harmonic parts of the spectrum of the song.

The HPSS algorithm separates the harmonic and the percussive part assuming that in a spectrogram the harmonic components are “smooth in temporal direction” and the percussive components are “smooth in frequency direction”. With a long time window Buyens et al. [2013] are capable to separate vocals and drums (appearing in the *percussive components*) from the other instruments (*harmonic components*).

One can note that dividing the spectrogram into those two parts for estimating the multitrack is sub-optimal. For example, the bass is an harmonic instrument and therefore would be attenuated even is an instrument that clearly contributes to the rhythm/beat. Object-based techniques such as SS (instrument based) are more appropriate than the HPSS approach (time-frequency smoothness based) proposed. SS algorithms are broadly used in the MIR research community for isolating instrument audio sources [Roebel et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2014a; Marxer and Janer, 2012]. Estimating the multitrack recording using object-based SS techniques instead of HPSS leads to more robust underlying assumptions.

Furthermore, [Buyens et al. \[2013\]](#) assess their approach doing perceptual tests with NH people with CIs simulated music excerpts, what is clearly sub-optimal. Perceptual tests with implanted people are needed to assess the validity of the proposed approach.

It does not exist any previous study trying to simplify classical music for improving CIs music experience. To our knowledge, this work represents the first steps towards improving classical music perception.

In this master thesis it is proposed to pre-process the music signal (with state of the art SS algorithms) to estimate the multitrack recording, what would allow then to approach the simplification problem in the same way as [Buyens et al. \[2014, 2013\]](#): remixing the signal to reduce the complexity of the music structures. Perceptual tests with CIs using popular and classical music are also going to be carried out to answer the posed research questions.

2.2 Source Separation

The SS problem in the signal processing field is defined as the extraction of the original component signals from a mixture where several signals have been combined together.

A good example is the estimation of a multitrack recording from a music mixture, the study case of this master thesis. Considering that one has a song from a CD or a live recording (mono or stereo) and aims to obtain the multitrack recording automatically; in fact, what one aims is to obtain is the signal for each of the independent source instruments separately: an stream of audio for each instrument playing.

FIGURE 2.2: *Music source separation example.*

SS techniques can also be applied to other fields such as bio-medicine, for example is used for measuring the fetal heart rate [\[De Lathauwer et al., 2000\]](#). This measurement can be

influenced by the mother's heart rate because the fetus is in her belly. As both hearts are independent sources, SS techniques are used into the EEG signal of the mother to isolate the fetal EEG.

2.2.1 Background

This brief introduction would allow the reader to understand where those technologies come from and its terminology, for further details in each of the algorithms one can refer to the cited original papers.

Along this master thesis matrices are going to be annotated in bold capital letters: *i.e.*, \mathbf{H} ; vectors with bold letters: *i.e.*, \mathbf{h} ; and scalar values in italics: *i.e.*, h .

In most of the SS literature it is assumed that the mixture spectrogram $\hat{\mathbf{V}} \in \mathfrak{R}^{F \times N}$ (an approximation of \mathbf{V} of the same size), results from the superposition of J source spectrograms \mathbf{V}_j of the same size as $\hat{\mathbf{V}}$. Where J is the number of sources (*i.e.* different instruments), F is the number of frequency bins and N is the number of time frames. Further, it is assumed that each of the spectrograms \mathbf{V}_j can be represented by the outer product of basis (\mathbf{w}_j of length F) with a time-varying gain (\mathbf{h}_j of length N). Most researchers assume that each j^{th} source base \mathbf{w}_j is characterized by K_j components.

$$\sum_{\forall j} K_j = K \quad (2.1)$$

Where K denotes the total number of components. Finally, that operation can be seen as a matrix product where $\mathbf{W} \in \mathfrak{R}^{F \times K}$ and \mathbf{H} is the activation matrix where $\mathbf{H} \in \mathfrak{R}^{K \times N}$.

$$\mathbf{V} \approx \hat{\mathbf{V}} = \sum_{j=1}^J \mathbf{V}_j = \sum_{j=1}^J \mathbf{w}_j^T \mathbf{h}_j = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{k=1}^{K_j} \mathbf{w}_{j,k}^T \mathbf{h}_{j,k} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{H} \quad (2.2)$$

SS methods based on the formulation above, differ in how the decomposition of \mathbf{V} is achieved, the most important ones rely on 3 main ideas: statistical independence of the sources, sparseness and non-negativity. Listed in historical order of appearance:

- Independent Subspace Analysis (ISA) [Casey and Westner, 2000]: this approach assumes statistical independence of sources. ISA is a relaxed Independent Component Analysis (ICA) [Hyvärinen et al., 2004] that separates the input signal into

additive sub components that are statistical independent. The advantage of ISA respect to ICA is that in the former the number of sensors does not need to be larger than or equal to the number of sources. That means, in audio, to have as many microphones as sources (when usually there is only one channel available). One of the problems of ISA is that decompositions can get negative values with difficult physical interpretation.

- Non Negative Sparse Coding (NNSC) [Hoyer, 2002]: assumes sparseness as a constraint for the activations and non-negativity for basis and activations. Those assumptions allow giving physical interpretation to the results.
- Non-Negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) [D.D.Lee and H.S.Seung, 2001]: an effective factorization method for decomposing \mathbf{V} constraining \mathbf{W} and \mathbf{H} to be non-negative (by means of multiplicative update rules), popularized that approach. Sparseness can be easily introduced by means of mathematical constraints into the cost function. The main drawback is its high computational cost for factorizing \mathbf{V} .

In order to improve the performance of the previously described algorithms Prior Subspace Analysis (PSA) [FitzGerald et al., 2003] was introduced; this method consists on learning previous knowledge about the sources by training the basis \mathbf{W} a priori. This approach is extremely interesting because the basis are tagged by default. This avoids the use of post-processing techniques to estimate the kind of source that represents each specific \mathbf{w}_j . One can train the system to recognize some specific sources, what improves significantly the results [Carabias-Orti et al., 2013; Roebel et al., 2015].

Some researchers introduced other prior knowledge into the matrix initialization of the factorization, those are called:

- Informed SS: This family of methods rely on prior information. Using the MIDI score for initializing \mathbf{H} or knowing in advance the number of J sources, improves the estimation (in terms of avoiding local minimas and reducing the computational cost). In contrast to those methods, blind SS do not consider any prior knowledge.

Despite the above mentioned methods are in an advanced research stage, a novel trend currently exists in the SS community and is not based on matrix decompositions. Those

novel methods are based on a deep learning, where the goal is to estimate directly the source mask using a classification model trained with *tones* of data. The novelty with the deep learning approaches is that they allow nonlinear relationships, what ends up with a more expressive model than the ones that assume linearity. Mainly, two techniques matched the NMF state of the art:

- Deep Neural Networks (DNN) [Huang et al., 2014b]: Enabling more than one hidden layer (from where appears the concept *deep*) the system is able to learn more complex representations from the training data. Training DNN is time consuming and requires a large amount of data, but once trained the model is faster than the iterative matrix decomposition models.
- Deep Recurrent Neural Networks (DRNN) [Huang et al., 2014a]: It is an extension of DNN where the temporal dependencies can also be modelled. While in DNN the nodes from one layer can only connect with nodes from the next layer, in DRNN recursive connections between nodes of the same layer are also allowed. Therefore the output state do not only depend on the input or previous layers but also on the internal information of the nets, containing a transformation of what the network has seen up to the current time step. This *memory* modelling is an interesting property for audio applications as the temporal context in musical perception is important.

Following subsections introduce more detailed information about the background and basics of the SS algorithms used in that master thesis: a general purpose state-of-the-art SS algorithm (NMF-like) called FASST [Ozerov et al., 2012] is used here as a base line algorithm for pop music and DRNN is introduced as a research topic. Remember here that the source separation task is only related to popular music. For orchestral music is still necessary to prove that a different mixing setup can help to improve CIs musical experience.

One would note that the introduction done for the FASST algorithm is much concrete than the one for deep learning. The former is a baseline algorithm already fully developed by the authors Ozerov et al. [2012]; while the latter is the research topic of the signal processing part of this master thesis. That is the reason why the introduction too deep learning for SS needs to be different: discussion oriented.

2.2.2 FASST

Flexible Audio Source Separation Toolbox (FASST)² is a general purpose framework able to model SS problems by simply setting properly the parameters of the library. Most SS frameworks are difficult to reuse as they are focused on modelling a specific problem. This software pretends to overcome that limitation providing a general and flexible framework. The aim of this subsection is to explain briefly its main characteristics, for further information see [Ozerov et al., 2012].

The global model is based on equation 2.2 but includes an extension motivated by the physics of the problem, each j^{th} source is characterized by an *excitation-filter model*:

$$\mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{V}_j^{\text{ex}} \odot \mathbf{V}_j^{\text{ft}} \quad (2.3)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise matrix multiplication, \mathbf{V}_j^{ex} corresponds to excitation spectral power and \mathbf{V}_j^{ft} to the filter spectral power. Figure 2.3 depicts an illustrative example that helps to understand the meaning of \mathbf{V}_j^{ex} and \mathbf{V}_j^{ft} .

FIGURE 2.3: Example extracted from [Ozerov et al., 2012]. Depicts how the excitation part (\mathbf{V}_j^{ex}) and the filter part (\mathbf{V}_j^{ft}) contribute to the source estimation.

The excitation spectral power \mathbf{V}_j^{ex} is further decomposed as *spectral patterns* \mathbf{E}_j^{ex} modulated by *time activation coefficients* \mathbf{P}_j^{ex} . The *spectral patterns* are linear combinations of narrow band spectral patterns \mathbf{W}_j^{ex} with weights \mathbf{U}_j^{ex} . Following the same idea, the *time activation coefficients* \mathbf{P}_j^{ex} are a combination of time-localized patterns \mathbf{H}_j^{ex} with weights \mathbf{G}_j^{ex} . The filter spectral power \mathbf{V}_j^{ft} is similarly expressed:

²<http://bass-db.gforge.inria.fr/fasst/>

$$\mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{V}_j^{ex} \odot \mathbf{V}_j^{ft} = \mathbf{E}_j^{ex} \mathbf{P}_j^{ex} \odot \mathbf{E}_j^{ft} \mathbf{P}_j^{ft} = \quad (2.4)$$

$$= (\mathbf{W}_j^{ex} \mathbf{U}_j^{ex} \mathbf{G}_j^{ex} \mathbf{H}_j^{ex}) \odot (\mathbf{W}_j^{ft} \mathbf{U}_j^{ft} \mathbf{G}_j^{ft} \mathbf{H}_j^{ft}) \quad (2.5)$$

Where the elements introduced above are defined in Figure 2.4:

Parameter subsets		Size	Range
$\theta_{j,1} = \mathbf{A}_j$	mixing parameters	$I \times R_j \times F \times N$	$\in \mathbb{C}$
$\theta_{j,2} = \mathbf{W}_j^{ex}$	ex. narrowband spectral patterns	$F \times L_j^{ex}$	$\in \mathbb{R}_+$
$\theta_{j,3} = \mathbf{U}_j^{ex}$	ex. spectral pattern weights	$L_j^{ex} \times K_j^{ex}$	$\in \mathbb{R}_+$
$\theta_{j,4} = \mathbf{G}_j^{ex}$	ex. time pattern weights	$K_j^{ex} \times M_j^{ex}$	$\in \mathbb{R}_+$
$\theta_{j,5} = \mathbf{H}_j^{ex}$	ex. time-localized patterns	$M_j^{ex} \times N$	$\in \mathbb{R}_+$
$\theta_{j,6} = \mathbf{W}_j^{ft}$	ft. narrowband spectral patterns	$F \times L_j^{ft}$	$\in \mathbb{R}_+$
$\theta_{j,7} = \mathbf{U}_j^{ft}$	ft. spectral pattern weights	$L_j^{ft} \times K_j^{ft}$	$\in \mathbb{R}_+$
$\theta_{j,8} = \mathbf{G}_j^{ft}$	ft. time pattern weights	$K_j^{ft} \times M_j^{ft}$	$\in \mathbb{R}_+$
$\theta_{j,9} = \mathbf{H}_j^{ft}$	ft. time-localized patterns	$M_j^{ft} \times N$	$\in \mathbb{R}_+$

FIGURE 2.4: Summary table: elements of the source model. Where I denotes the number of channels, R_j refers to the rank of the co variance matrix of the j^{th} spatial component and L are the number of narrow bands. Extracted from [Ozerov et al., 2012].

One can note that the FASST model is a general case of equation 2.2. FASST assumes a general formulation that can be adapted in each case, *i.e.* using only a part of the model ($\mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{V}_j^{ex}$; see Figure 2.5) or fixing \mathbf{E}_j^{ft} and \mathbf{E}_j^{ex} to some learned spectral patterns taking advantage of the PSA method. Note that the representation proposed in FASST is extremely versatile, in the sense that one can apply constraints to many specific aspects of the signal such as: temporal evolution, spectral shape or impose an harmonic model.

Given the above mentioned model, FASST estimation of the source is achieved in two steps as shown in Figure 2.6:

- Step 1. Given initial parameter values θ_{init} , the model parameters θ are estimated from the mixture \mathbf{X} using an iterative Generalized Expectation Maximization (GEM) [Demrsrsa et al., 1977] algorithm; where each iteration is achieved by means of Multiplicative Update (MU) [D.D.Lee and H.S.Seung, 2001] rules inspired from the NMF methodology.
- Step 2. Given the mixture \mathbf{X} and the estimated model parameters θ , source estimates \mathbf{V}_j are computed using Wiener filtering [Carabias-Orti et al., 2013].

Chapter 3.1 details the specific implementation of FASST used along that master thesis.

FIGURE 2.5: *Example extracted from [Ozerov et al., 2012]. Depicts how the model of the excitation part (\mathbf{V}_j^{ex}) behaves.*

FIGURE 2.6: *Schema from [Ozerov et al., 2012] where the FASST estimation method is depicted.*

2.2.3 Deep learning: from neural networks to deep recurrent neural networks

Neural Networks (NN), with a feedforward architecture, is a biological inspired machine learning algorithm used to approximate an unknown function from data. NN is a system of interconnected *neurons*; one can see an example in Figure 2.7.

Typically, any NN is formed by units (neurons) that are grouped into three layers (groups of neurons): input layers, hidden layers and output layers [Pascanu, 2015]. In Figure 2.7 units are expressed as circles and layers are grouped by columns of circles: input layer (red circles), hidden layer (blue circles) and output layer (green circles).

FIGURE 2.7: *Basic NN architecture.*

A NN outputs a prediction $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \in \mathfrak{R}^{1 \times d_{output}}$ of the form:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{W}^{(2)}\mathbf{h}^{(1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(2)} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\mathbf{h}^{(1)} = \sigma^{(1)}(\mathbf{W}^{(1)}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{b}^{(1)}) \quad (2.7)$$

where the weight matrices are denoted by $\mathbf{W}^{(l)} \in \mathfrak{R}^{d_{(l-1)} \times d_{(l)}}$ together with the bias vector $\mathbf{b}^{(l)} \in \mathfrak{R}^{1 \times d_{(l)}}$ and $\mathbf{x} \in \mathfrak{R}^{1 \times d_{input}}$. With l representing the index of the current layer, going from $1 \leq l \leq (L-1)$; in conventional NN $L = 3$: $1 \leq l \leq 2$. One can observe that the dimension d can be different in each layer, input and output; this is the reason why $d_{(l)}$ is denoted with the subindex l .

Each neuron is characterized by a non linear activation function $\sigma^{(l)}$ fixed beforehand and can be layer specific or the same function for all layers. Three popular activation functions $\sigma^{(l)}$ are the sigmoid, tanh or rectifier linear unit (*a.k.a.* RELU):

$$sigmoid(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (2.8)$$

$$tanh(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}} \quad (2.9)$$

$$RELU(x) = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

Huang et al. [2014a] found that the RELU function gave them better results for the singing voice separation task. Note that the RELU function is related to the non-negativity property characteristic of NMF that provided so many good results in music source separation tasks [Carabias-Orti et al., 2013; Roebel et al., 2015].

The goal here is to separate the sources of a song. Normally songs have variable-length and to train a NN with high-dimensional inputs is expensive. Using small temporal context windows increases computation efficiency and prevents overfitting (because one has more data) [Maas et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2014a].

When using small context windows in conventional NN it is assumed that short context regions are sufficient to model $f : \hat{\mathbf{y}} = f(\mathbf{x})$. This is a wrong assumption since human hearing perception is clearly related to the context defined by the past events [Maas et al., 2012]. One possible solution is to increase the contextual window, trying to find a compromise for the context size. But another (smarter) possibility is to use Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN): allowing recurrent connections inside the NN model. In that way, one avoids big input sizes while allowing to model temporal dependencies over unspecified (and potentially infinite) intervals of time [Pascanu, 2015; Huang et al., 2014a]. In Figure 2.8 the RNN architecture is introduced in three equivalent ways.

FIGURE 2.8: *Basic RNN architecture represented in three equivalent ways. Left: from the neurons point of view. Although not all the recurrent connections are drawn, theoretically all neurons of the same layer can be connected recursively. Center: from the layers point of view. Right: unfolded layers point of view. Since there is only one hidden layer, the layer index $\mathbf{h}^{(l)}$ is omitted.*

One can observe that the hidden activation depends on the previous hidden activation and the input: $\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(1)} = f(\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}^{(1)}, \mathbf{x}_{(t)})$. Note that for RNN one needs to introduce the subindex t to denote the time-frame where one is located. Consequently, the equations for RNN case are then:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{(t)} = \mathbf{W}^{(2)}\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(2)} \quad (2.11)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(1)} = \sigma^{(1)}(\mathbf{W}^{(1)}\mathbf{x}_{(t)} + \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(1)}\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}^{(1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(1)}) \quad (2.12)$$

Where $\mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(l)} \in \mathfrak{R}^{d^{(l)} \times d^{(l)}}$ denotes the recurrent weights connections. Note that $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{(t)}$ remains the same as in equation 2.6 and only $\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(1)}$ changes to be recursive.

Finally, one last consideration: perhaps a model having only one single hidden layer is not sufficiently expressive. A NN is considered deep if it has more than one hidden layer. Deep learning is becoming popular since there is enough computational resources and data to train [Ngiam et al., 2011]. Intuitively, in the literature is argued that depth allows the construction of hierarchical features, where the features from the higher layers are more complex and constructed from the summary/interpretation of the layers below [Bengio, 2009; Pascanu, 2015]. But empirical proofs of the usefulness of depth can also be given. Recently, many deep learning approaches obtained state of the art results in different research areas such as: music processing [Huang et al., 2014b,a], speech processing [Mohamed et al., 2011] or image processing [Goodfellow et al., 2013].

Given the formulation above, the unique implication for constructing a Deep NN (DNN), recurrent or not, is to have more than one hidden layer, thus: $L > 3$. This gives the general formulation for Deep RNN (DRNN) defined as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{(t)} = \mathbf{W}^{(L-1)}\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(L-2)} + \mathbf{b}^{(L-1)} \quad (2.13)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(l)} = \sigma^{(l)}(\mathbf{W}^{(l)}\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(l-1)} + \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(l)}\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}^{(l)} + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}) \quad (2.14)$$

$$\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(1)} = \sigma^{(1)}(\mathbf{W}^{(1)}\mathbf{x}_{(t)} + \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(1)}\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}^{(1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(1)}) \quad (2.15)$$

Setting $L = 3$ it rises the specific case of RNN; and setting $L = 3$ and $\mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(l)} = \mathbf{0}$ one defines a feedforward NN.

Note that for feedforward DNN the *depth* is well defined; but for RNN the *depth* can be ambiguous since one can argue that by definition RNN are already *depth* due to its (potentially infinite) recurrent connections. Nonetheless, Pascanu et al. [2013] noticed that there are three kind of connections in RNN that can be made *deeper*: input-to-hidden ($\mathbf{x}_{(t)} \rightarrow \mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(1)}$), hidden-to-hidden ($\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}^{(l)} \rightarrow \mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(l)}$) and hidden-to-output ($\mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(L-2)} \rightarrow$

$\mathbf{y}_{(t)}$). Those connections are *shallow* in the sense that it does not exist more than one intermediate nonlinear layer in-between. Several architectures can construct a *deeper* RNN, for example Huang et al. [2014a] introduced *depth* in two parts of the RNN for the singing voice separation task: input-to-hidden and hidden-to-output. The former allows complex representations (can be viewed also as a summary) of the input independently of the information coming from the recurrent connections. Previous work has shown that higher-level representations of deep networks tend to better interpret the underlying factors of variation than the original input [Pascanu et al., 2013]. The hidden-to-output *depth* seems to be useful for disentangling the factors involved in the hidden state, making it easier to predict the output.

Finally, empirical results also support the hypothesis that using DRNN improves performance in audio applications. Results provided by Maas et al. [2012] in Table 3 show a comparison between NN, RNN, DNN and DRNN and one can observe how determinant is the impact of using recurrent and deep architectures. Furthermore in Huang et al. [2014a] in Tables 4 and 5 compares DNN with different DRNN architectures showing that DRNN models achieve better results compared to DNN models.

As previously mentioned, the signal processing part of this master thesis is focused on the use of DRNN. After the previous discussion, one hopes that the reader is also convinced about the theoretical benefits of using DRNN.

2.2.3.1 Algorithms for training DRNN: non-convex optimization problem

In optimization, line search is a common iterative approach to find a local minimum \mathbf{W}^* of a cost function $e(\mathbf{W})$. Line search algorithms first find a direction \mathbf{d}_k where the cost function will descend and then computes a step μ_k towards that direction. Those iterative algorithms are formulated as follows:

$$\mathbf{W}_{k+1} = \mathbf{W}_k + \mu_k \mathbf{d}_k \quad (2.16)$$

and only differ on how do they compute the descent direction. Where k denotes the current iteration. Note that this method ensures to reach a global minima in case that the cost function is convex, but for non-convex optimization problems (like DRNN) line

search only can reach a local minimum. The generalization properties of such local minimum only depends on the initialization \mathbf{W}_o .

Mainly, two big families of methods exist:

- Gradient Descend: a first order method. Finds the direction \mathbf{d}_k by means of computing the gradient of the cost function with respect to the parameters to optimize. The local minima is always into the opposite direction that the gradient points; therefore, the negative of the gradient points the direction with the steepest descend.

$$\mathbf{W}_{k+1} = \mathbf{W}_k - \mu_k \nabla e(\mathbf{W}_k) \quad (2.17)$$

- Newton's Methods: the second order family methods. Uses information from the second derivative of the cost function, expressed in the Hessian matrix (\mathbf{H}):

$$\mathbf{W}_{k+1} = \mathbf{W}_k - \mu_k \mathbf{H}_k^{-1} \nabla e(\mathbf{W}_k) \quad (2.18)$$

By taking the curvature information into account (the Hessian), the Newton's Method re-scales the gradient in a way that can find a better direction [Martens, 2010]. 2nd order methods are faster because they can leave plateaus easily, finding a local minimum with less iterations [Ngiam et al., 2011; Martens, 2010]. But these are computationally expensive: computing \mathbf{H}^{-1} when optimizing a big amount of parameters (such as in DRNN) becomes an unfeasible problem for a computer (huge matrices to compute and invert) [Nocedal and Wright, 2006]. Quasi-Newton's methods iteratively estimate \mathbf{H}^{-1} ; but note that if one directly estimates the inverse, \mathbf{H} do not needs to be inverted and one skips these tedious calculations. L-BFGS uses that *trick* in order to estimate iteratively an approximation of \mathbf{H}^{-1} based on: most recent iterations of \mathbf{H}^{-1} 's approximation and the change in gradient between iterations [Apostolopoulou et al., 2009; Nocedal and Wright, 2006].

A common way of training NN is by means of line search using the back-propagation algorithm. In order to introduce the back-propagation algorithm in a *friendly* way, the mathematical justifications are given assuming Gradient Descend and feedforward NN. The here provided derivation studies the weights individually ($W_{ij}^{(l)}$), for simplicity and

better understanding. Note that the partial derivatives are equivalently expressed with the gradient in matricial representation:

$$\nabla e(\mathbf{W}) : \quad \frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial W_{ij}^{(l)}} \quad \forall l, i, j \quad (2.19)$$

To optimize the weights $W_{ij}^{(l)}$, Gradient Descend algorithm follows the direction of the partial derivative applying the following update rule:

$$W_{ij}^{(l)} \leftarrow W_{ij}^{(l)} - \mu \frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial W_{ij}^{(l)}} \quad \forall l, i, j \quad (2.20)$$

where $e(\cdot)$ denotes the cost function, l denotes the current layer, $i \in [0, 1, \dots, d_{(l-1)}]$ and $j \in [0, 1, \dots, d_{(l)}]$ represent the row and and columns index of the matrices $W_{ij}^{(l)}$.

The back-propagation algorithm is a an efficient method to compute $\frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial W_{ij}^{(l)}}$, the unique unknown parameter of equation 2.20 (given that $W_{ij}^{(l)}$ is previously initialized and μ is a fixed step).

A connection between two neurons can be defined as follows:

FIGURE 2.9: *Formalizing the connection between two neurons to define s_j .*

where:

$$s_j^{(l)} = h_i^{(l-1)} W_{ij}^{(l)} \quad h_j^{(l)} = \sigma^{(l)}(s_j^{(l)}) \quad (2.21)$$

For computing $\frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial W_{ij}^{(l)}}$, the chain rule is applied taking advantage of the intermediate quantity $s_j^{(l)}$:

$$\frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial W_{ij}^{(l)}} = \frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial s_j^{(l)}} \frac{\partial s_j^{(l)}}{\partial W_{ij}^{(l)}} = \delta_j^{(l)} h_i^{(l-1)} \quad (2.22)$$

Note that using the chain rule, the second term of the chain is easily solvable; but the first one (named $\delta_j^{(l)}$) still remains challenging. Then, the Gradient Descend update rule gets the following form:

$$W_{ij}^{(l)} \leftarrow W_{ij}^{(l)} - \mu \delta_j^{(l)} h_i^{(l-1)} \quad \forall l, i, j \quad (2.23)$$

Since $h_i^{(l-1)}$ can be computed propagating the input value through the net (this step is known as *forward propagation*), only $\delta_j^{(l)}$ remains unknown and is computed by back-propagating the error through the net.

Studying the last layer one realizes that the error can be computed (y_j is known) and is function of $s_j^{(L-1)}$ (therefore, can be derived):

$$\delta_j^{(L-1)} = \frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial s_j^{(L-1)}} = \frac{\partial e(\hat{y}_j, y_j)}{\partial s_j^{(L-1)}} = \frac{\partial e(h_j^{(L-1)}, y_j)}{\partial s_j^{(L-1)}} = \frac{\partial e(\sigma^{(L-1)}(s_j^{(L-1)}), y_j)}{\partial s_j^{(L-1)}} \quad (2.24)$$

Remember that $1 \leq l \leq L - 1$, this is the reason why the last layer is the $L - 1$.

At that point, we are capable to compute $\delta_j^{(L-1)}$: finding the partial derivative of $e(\sigma^{(L-1)}(s_j^{(L-1)}), y_j)$ and evaluating accordingly. Next step is to back-propagate $\delta_j^{(L-1)}$ through the other layers of the network. For computing $\delta_i^{(l-1)}$ the chain rule is applied; one will observe how the terms of the chain rule end up with solvable partial derivatives and familiar terms. In Figure 2.10 one can observe the gradient flow when back-propagating the deltas and how $s_i^{(l-1)}$ depends on $\forall j$ previous neurons. That's the reason why one needs to sum up overall neurons when applying the chain rule:

$$\delta_i^{(l-1)} = \frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial s_i^{(l-1)}} = \sum_{j=1}^{d^{(l)}} \frac{\partial e(\mathbf{W})}{\partial s_j^{(l)}} \frac{\partial s_j^{(l)}}{\partial h_i^{(l-1)}} \frac{\partial h_i^{(l-1)}}{\partial s_i^{(l-1)}} = \sum_{j=1}^{d^{(l)}} \delta_j^{(l)} W_{ij}^{(l)} \sigma'^{(l-1)}(s_i^{(l-1)}) = \quad (2.25)$$

$$= \sigma'^{(l-1)}(s_i^{(l-1)}) \sum_{j=1}^{d^{(l)}} \delta_j^{(l)} W_{ij}^{(l)} = \delta_i^{(l-1)} \quad (2.26)$$

where $\sigma'(\cdot)$ denotes the derivative of $\sigma(\cdot)$. Equation 2.26 links $\delta_i^{(l-1)}$ with $\delta_j^{(l)}$, since $\delta_j^{(L-1)}$ is known, this equation shows how to back-propagate the deltas.

FIGURE 2.10: *Gradient flow when back-propagating the deltas.*

Finally, the back-propagation algorithm for NN with Gradient Descent is formulated as follows:

- 1: Initialize weights and define μ
- 2: **for** $t=0,1,2,\dots$ **do**
- 3: compute all $h_j^{(l)}$ (forward propagation)
- 4: compute all $\delta_j^{(l)}$ (back-propagation))
- 5: update the weights accordingly: $W_{ij}^{(l)} \leftarrow W_{ij}^{(l)} - \mu \delta_j^{(l)} h_i^{(l-1)} \quad \forall l, i, j$
- 6: iterate until it is time to stop
- 7: Return the final $W_{ij}^{(l)}$

Note that one can extend the back-propagation algorithm to L-BFGS because for estimating the hessian approximation one needs: the most recent iterations of \mathbf{H}^{-1} 's approximation (or a proper initialization) and the change in gradient between iterations (given by the back-propagation algorithm). For doing such minimizations, the *minFunc.m*³ function of Mark Schmidt is used.

But the back-propagation algorithm for feedforward NN cannot be directly used to train RNN because the error pass assumes feedforward connections. The solution to that problem is to “unfold” the recurrent network in time: in Figure 2.8 one can observe how to “unfold” the RNN to create an equivalent feedforward NN. Once the equivalent feedforward NN is constructed, the back-propagation algorithm can be used. This method is called Back-Propagation Through Time (BPTT).

³<http://www.cs.ubc.ca/~schmidtm/Software/minFunc.html>

2.2.3.2 Challenges when training Deep and Recurrent NN

For a long time, DNN and RNN didn't perform as well as shallow NN. Although the theoretical benefits of using DNN (more expressive) and RNN (able to model temporal dependencies), they did not provide practical advantages because when the error flows backwards through the net tends to either explode or vanish.

In particular, what happens in DNN is that later layers in the network are learning well but early layers often get stuck and learn almost nothing (because the gradient has vanished and do not propagates properly through those). So: lower layers will not receive much of the training signal to learn [Hochreiter et al., 2001; Glorot and Bengio, 2010]. Remember (equation 2.26) that the back-propagation algorithm passes the error backwards through the deltas:

$$\delta_i^{(l-1)} = \sigma'^{(l-1)}(s_i^{l-1}) \sum_{j=1}^{d^{(l)}} \delta_j^{(l)} W_{ij}^{(l)} \quad (2.27)$$

with a multiplicative dependency between $\delta_j^{(l)}$ and $W_{ij}^{(l)}$. Note that if $W_{ij}^{(l)}$ is initialized with small random numbers [Huang et al., 2014b; He et al., 2015; Glorot and Bengio, 2010], after back-propagating the error through several layers the error can easily vanish. Also note that if $W_{ij}^{(l)}$ is initialized as a big number this is not a solution because the gradient will explode.

A way to control that the deltas do not vanish is by means of initializing them in a way that its variance is controlled (it does not vanish nor explode) under a desirable range. A common heuristic is to initialize:

$$\mathbf{W} \sim U[-0.01, 0.01] \quad (2.28)$$

0.01 value is proposed because seems reasonable to assume that approximately half of the weights will be positive and half of them will be negative after normalizing the input data. Therefore, having values closed to zero seems the *best guess*. Randomness is introduced to break the symmetry, because if all weights are initialized to be zero all gradients would be the same.

One problem with the above proposal is that the variance at a neuron's output grows with the number of inputs (likely to explode). A first approach to solve this problem

was to modify the variance depending on the number of inputs (n_{in}):

$$\mathbf{W} \sim U\left[-\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}\right] \quad (2.29)$$

But after a more careful analysis, [Glorot and Bengio \[2010\]](#) formalized a more accurate initialization. Considering also the number of output neurons (n_{out}) in the next layer:

$$\mathbf{W} \sim U\left[-\frac{\sqrt{6}}{\sqrt{n_{in} + n_{out}}}, \frac{\sqrt{6}}{\sqrt{n_{in} + n_{out}}}\right] \quad (2.30)$$

This is motivated by doing the same variance analysis but considering both: forward and back-propagated gradients. [Glorot and Bengio \[2010\]](#) work is based on analyzing the gradients when using as $\sigma(\cdot)$: *sigmoid*(\cdot), *tanh*(\cdot) and *softsign*(\cdot).

But recently, *RELU*(\cdot) (linear rectifiers) have provided outstanding results [[He et al., 2015](#); [Krizhevsky et al., 2012](#)]. In [He et al. \[2015\]](#), they did a similar analysis as [Glorot and Bengio \[2010\]](#) but considering RELUs, concluding that the most appropriate initialization is:

$$\mathbf{W} \sim U\left[-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{n_{in}}}, \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{n_{in}}}\right] \quad (2.31)$$

RNNs suffer similarly the gradient vanish/explode problem [[Hochreiter et al., 2001](#)] and they cannot learn long temporal dependencies. Let's focus on trying to understand how much can the net learn when incorporating the recurrent connections. For doing so, we want to minimize the error at a time step t *w.r.t.* \mathbf{W}_{rec} . Assuming an unfolded shallow RNN ($L = 3$), the error flow paths coming from the past are highlighted in [Figure 2.11](#), from where one can deduce the following expressions from each path:

$$\frac{\partial e(\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t), \mathbf{y}(t))}{\partial \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(1)}} = \frac{\partial e(\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t), \mathbf{y}(t))}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)} \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(1)}} + \quad (2.32)$$

$$+ \frac{\partial e(\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t), \mathbf{y}(t))}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)} \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t-1)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t-1)}{\partial \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(1)}} + \quad (2.33)$$

$$+ \frac{\partial e(\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t), \mathbf{y}(t))}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)} \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t-1)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t-1)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t-2)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t-2)}{\partial \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(1)}} + \dots \quad (2.34)$$

FIGURE 2.11: RNN error paths to follow (in three different colors) when applying the chain rule at time step t until \mathbf{W}_{rec} . One can observe how the error from the past flows.

Summarized as follows:

$$\frac{\partial e(\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t), \mathbf{y}(t))}{\partial \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(1)}} = \sum_{k=1}^t \frac{\partial e(\hat{\mathbf{y}}(t), \mathbf{y}(t))}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)} \frac{\partial \hat{\mathbf{y}}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(k)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(k)}{\partial \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(1)}} \quad (2.35)$$

where:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(k)} = \prod_{s=k+1}^t \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(s)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(s-1)} = \left\{ \mathbf{h}^{(l)}(t) = \sigma^{(l)}(\mathbf{W}^{(l)} \mathbf{h}^{(l-1)}(t) + \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(l)} \mathbf{h}^{(l)}(t-1) + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}) \right\} = \quad (2.36)$$

$$= \prod_{s=k+1}^t \mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(l)T} \text{diag}[\sigma'^{(1)}(\mathbf{h}^{(1)}(s-1))] \quad (2.37)$$

Furthermore, if one upper bounds the norm of $\frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(s)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(s-1)}$ by a constant value:

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(s)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(s-1)} \right\| \leq \|\mathbf{W}_{rec}^{(l)T}\| \left\| \text{diag}[\sigma'^{(1)}(\mathbf{h}^{(1)}(s-1))] \right\| \leq \gamma_{W_{rec}} \gamma_{\sigma}. \quad (2.38)$$

then,

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(t)}{\partial \mathbf{h}^{(1)}(k)} \right\| \leq (\gamma_{W_{rec}} \gamma_{\sigma})^{(t-k)} \quad (2.39)$$

From equation 2.39 one can observe that $\left\| \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}_t^{(1)}}{\partial \mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}} \right\|$ depends exponentially on $\gamma_{W_{rec}} \gamma_\sigma$:

- *if* $\gamma_{W_{rec}} \gamma_\sigma \gg 1$: $\left\| \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}_t^{(1)}}{\partial \mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}} \right\|$ explodes.
- *if* $\gamma_{W_{rec}} \gamma_\sigma \ll 1$: $\left\| \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}_t^{(1)}}{\partial \mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}} \right\|$ vanishes.
- *if* $\gamma_{W_{rec}} \gamma_\sigma \approx 1$: the error can be propagated and the net can be trained.

If the gradient vanishes or explodes, means that the input at stage k do not influence the output at stage t , then the information from the past would not help: RNN cannot remember. Therefore, the initialization of W_{rec} and the choice of the $\sigma(\cdot)$ is important.

A popular (and successful) way of solving the gradient vanish/explode when training RNN is Long Short Term Memory (LSTM).

LSTM substitute the neurons of the NN (characterized by a non-linear function $\sigma(\cdot)$) for a much more complex cell (see Figure 2.12) that allows to write/read/erase the temporal memory inherent in RNNs avoiding that the gradient explodes or vanish when training.

FIGURE 2.12: LSTM cell with the input gate (write memory), forget gate (erase memory) and output gate (read memory). All inputs are the same: \mathbf{x}_t (or \mathbf{h}_t) and \mathbf{h}_{t-1} ; the output is \mathbf{h}_t .

One can observe that the cell has several gates: input gate (for writing to memory), forget gate (to erase the memory) and output gate (to read out from memory). Those act as control signals that (by means of a multiplication) determine when to write/erase/read. Note that introducing this cell structure based on gates, the net is able to break this multiplication chain (equation 2.36):

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{h}_t^{(1)}}{\partial \mathbf{h}_k^{(1)}} = \prod_{s=k+1}^t \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}_s^{(1)}}{\partial \mathbf{h}_{s-1}^{(1)}} \quad (2.40)$$

and theoretically the net can be trained because one can skip the gradient vanish/explode problem. But one do not know the parameters that define when to write/read/erase and those are learned from data, as well. In other words, the net continuously feeds error back until they are trained to cut off the value. This model has shown to be very successful, *i.e.*: in handwriting recognition [Graves et al., 2009] or speech recognition [Graves et al., 2013].

But recently, Le et al. [2015] have introduced another simpler method that has shown to provide similar results as LSTM: Identity Recurrent Neural Networks (IRNN). This method is called Identity RNN because \mathbf{W}_{rec} is initialized to be the identity matrix. The authors argue that:

The identity initialization has the very desirable property that when the error derivatives for the hidden units are back-propagated through time they remain constant provided no extra error-derivatives are added. This is the same behavior as LSTMs when their forget gates are set so that there is no decay and it makes it easy to learn very long-range temporal dependencies.

But the identity initialization always acts feeding back the output of the neuron, meaning that the neuron keeps adding *infinitely*. This is good for long-term memory problems, but can be an issue for short-term memory problems. To limit IRNN's memory the \mathbf{W}_{rec} identity initialization can be attenuated. Somehow, one could say that we are inducing the gradient to vanish in a controlled way. Le et al. [2015] provide their results using RNN and RELUs, showing competitive results comparable to LSTM.

2.2.3.3 Final discussion

Huang et al. [2014a] reported an efficient DRNN model for separating the vocals from the music. We found such results remarkable but in our opinion the initialization is sub-optimal. They are considering RELUs and the initialization scheme is based on Glorot and Bengio [2010] proposal (thought for other $\sigma(\cdot)$'s, not for RELUs). Furthermore, the problem of having vanishing/exploding gradients while training RNN was not discussed nor mentioned in their publications. May be interesting to take a look closely to those issues to further improve Huang et al. [2014a] results.

For doing so, several initialization schemes will be studied along this master thesis. For the feedforward connections the initialization proposed by [He et al. \[2015\]](#) is used (since we are using RELUs) and compared to the initialization proposed by [Glorot and Bengio \[2010\]](#). IRNN, attenuated IRNN and several random initialization are going to be studied for initializing the recurrent connections (\mathbf{W}_{rec}). This is the main research corpus and is described in Chapter 3.2.

In other words, the signal processing part of this master thesis studies how several initializations (theoretically motivated) affect the singing voice source separation task for trying to improve the encouraging results provided by [Huang et al. \[2014a\]](#).

Along that work we are going to be using RELUs, the net is optimized using L-BFGS and back-propagating the errors through time.

Chapter 3

Source Separation

Implementation

Two SS algorithms are used for separating popular music: FASST [Ozerov et al., 2012] (as a baseline NMF algorithm) and DRNN [Huang et al., 2014a] (as a signal processing research topic). All pop songs are conformed by: leading voice, harmonic part (guitar, piano and/or organ), bass and/or drums. Along that section, the implementation details of each algorithm are exposed.

Results are given evaluating the model with the same test dataset composed by songs used in the second perceptual experiment (see Table 4.6). Source separation errors are quantified by several objective measures: Signal-to-Interference Ratio (SIR), Signal-to-Distortion Ratio (SDR), and Signal-to-Artifacts Ratio (SAR). SIR describe interference errors coming from other sources. Distortion errors are quantified by the SDR measure and the artifacts errors are quantified by the SAR. All those are measured in dBs and computed using the BSS Eval Toolbox [Vincent et al., 2006]. All runs are computed with the same machine, a regular laptop with an i5 processor and 4Gb of RAM; therefore, run times can be compared.

SS algorithms for orchestral music are not considered since experiments with CI users and NH listeners use the original multitracks.

3.1 FASST: pop music source separation

Here it is described how FASST is set for separating the bass, drums, melody and the remaining instruments from a stereo music recording. This implementation is available online¹ written in Matlab, in Ozerov et al. [2012] at *Section V.C* the authors extensively explain the details of this implementation that relies on two main concepts:

- Having prior knowledge about the sources to label them automatically (PSA).
- Joint modelling of all sources instead of a cascading approach (separating the drums, then the melody, etc.).

The sound scene is modelled with 12 sources: 4 sources representing the bass, 4 sources the drums and 4 sources modelling other instruments. Each of the source spectrograms \mathbf{V}_j of the bass and drums are constrained to $\mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{W}_j^{ex} \mathbf{G}_j^{ex}$ with \mathbf{G}_j^{ex} being adaptive and \mathbf{W}_j^{ex} being fixed and pre-trained from isolated bass and drum samples from the RWC music database [Goto et al., 2003]. The source spectrograms \mathbf{V}_j corresponding to the melody and to the remaining instruments are constrained to $\mathbf{V}_j = \mathbf{W}_j^{ex} \mathbf{U}_j^{ex} \mathbf{G}_j^{ex}$ where \mathbf{U}_j^{ex} and \mathbf{G}_j^{ex} are adaptive and \mathbf{W}_j^{ex} is a fixed dictionary representing the narrow band spectral patterns modelling the harmonic pitch. The decompositions are obtained over an ERB spectrogram (providing higher low-frequency resolution than the STFT, desired for modelling drums and bass), considering all twelve \mathbf{V}_j models together, with random initialization to all the adaptive parameters and in an NMF fashion.

Each of the sources are reconstructed by summing its corresponding source estimates (*i.e.*: summing the 4 bass estimations or the 4 drums estimations) and the melody is reconstructed by choosing the most energetic source of the 4 sources modelling other instruments. For simplicity of the study this work assumes that a lead singing voice is present in all mixes; so, one expect from the algorithm to detect the singing voice as melody. But this is not necessarily always true because using this energy criteria a strong guitar riff accompaniment can be also detected as main melody. Therefore, the way of detecting the singing voice is sub optimal. To further improve this algorithm for the singing voice case, may be helpful to incorporate a human voice source-filter model over \mathbf{V}_j .

¹http://bass-db.gforge.inria.fr/fasst/FASST_version_v1.zip

FASST can also exploit the panning information from stereo audio files. Having two channels of information helps the algorithm to get to a better solution. In order to get better separations, the stereo mixings have the following configuration:

$$L : 0.75 \cdot \textit{Voice} + 0.25 \cdot \textit{Other} + 0.5 \cdot \textit{Drums} + 0.5 \cdot \textit{Bass}$$

$$R : 0.25 \cdot \textit{Voice} + 0.75 \cdot \textit{Other} + 0.5 \cdot \textit{drums} + 0.5 \cdot \textit{bass}$$

It is possible to do such mixing because the multitrack recordings are available. The multitrack recordings are used to compute the objective measures that show the quality of the separations and to configure the perceptual experiments to measure NH listeners and CI users.

The window size of the initial STFT analysis (before the ERB mapping) is of 2048 samples, window overlapping of 1024 samples and FFT size of 2048 samples.

3.1.1 Results

The six *estimated* multitrack recordings (detailed in Table 4.6) used along the perceptual experiments are separated with the FASST algorithm. Therefore, all conclusions extracted from the perceptual experiments are subject to the objective measures shown here in Table 3.1 and Table 3.2.

Note that the FASST algorithm always outputs 4 sources: bass, drums, melody and other. When the original sound is conformed by less sources (*i.e.* 2 sources: piano and voice), the remaining FASST outputs are compared to silence (zeros) signals. That is the reason why in Table 3.1 for some sources there are such bad results (≤ -30 dBs), because the bass and drums outputs are compared to silence (zeros) signals. The original multitrack is compared to the output of the algorithm without any kind of normalization.

But when using the *estimated* multitrack for the perceptual experiments with NH listeners and CI users, the background instruments are grouped. Such grouping ends up with a two channels configuration: vocals+instruments. This is done to keep the study simple since there are songs with more than one background instrument. The results shown in Table 3.2 quantify how well the separations used in the perceptual experiments are.

		Hall	Bef	Mic2	Jud2	Jude	Dock
SDR	Bass	-31.6312	-34.9845	-34.0112	-35.8745	3.5414	0.7717
	Drums	-29.5553	-31.5747	-35.5119	-37.9638	-9.4664	-9.1025
	Guitar	10.51	3.7439	3.6917	-2.077	2.2526	4.2366
	Vocals	11.977	3.9668	9.8807	3.6692	6.9065	3.7151
SIR	Bass	-27.7736	-31.7499	-33.3552	-35.4105	4.4999	2.1853
	Drums	-27.6583	-30.3387	-33.0213	-34.8863	-6.5047	-6.2238
	Guitar	27.8948	19.7058	24.0025	18.8084	12.1385	15.1199
	Vocals	30.211	23.5004	32.4858	31.8757	17.6197	13.8027
SAR	Bass	-1.5487	-0.4346	7.8786	9.4802	11.8924	8.3876
	Drums	2.6218	4.829	1.1124	-0.132	0.9742	1.1964
	Guitar	10.5971	3.9016	3.7496	-1.9847	2.9807	4.7378
	Vocals	12.0469	4.0348	9.9071	3.6786	7.3661	4.3403

TABLE 3.1: FASST: 4 channels BSS objective measures.

-	Target (vocals)			Other (background)		
Song	SDR	SIR	SAR	SDR	SIR	SAR
Befo	3.966837	23.715669	4.031517	4.662717	5.735679	12.287757
Dock	3.713796	16.380930	4.054191	11.619106	13.964568	15.585651
Hall	11.977024	30.411642	12.043700	10.575422	12.573115	15.142345
Jud2	3.669180	33.726115	3.675310	7.359748	8.372689	14.768165
Jude	6.906527	19.568427	7.196129	14.662597	17.425012	18.013663
Mic2	9.880727	33.228957	9.902927	11.320928	13.004465	16.463326
Global	5.991409	26.635368	6.121139	9.928836	11.672339	15.433286
Time	4h 39min (source separation) + 2min (evaluation)					

TABLE 3.2: FASST: 2 channels BSS objective measures.

The global measurement is the mean weighted by the length of each song (for each objective measure). Those results are the baseline objective measures to beat using DRNN.

These results will serve us to compare performance with alternative algorithms such as DRNN.

One can observe how the SIR values are rather high. This is because the FASST algorithm is able to exploit the stereo mixing configuration used:

$$L : 0.75 \cdot Voice + 0.25 \cdot Other + 0.5 \cdot Drums + 0.5 \cdot Bass$$

$$R : 0.25 \cdot Voice + 0.75 \cdot Other + 0.5 \cdot drums + 0.5 \cdot bass$$

From those two channels input, FASST is able to get an really good SIR performance.

3.2 DRNN: pop music source separation

3.2.1 Baseline DRNN implementation

This implementation is based on the work (and corresponding Matlab code ²) published by Huang et al. [2014a]. Their DRNN models are trained using a chinese karaoke (MIR1K) dataset. This training data is different than our study case: separating the leading voice of western popular music. That is the reason why along this work our neural nets are optimized using the training data³ provided by the Signal Separation Evaluation Campaign 2015 (SiSEC-2015), which is closer to our requirements. This training dataset consists of 50 songs, with a duration ranging from 2 minutes and 22 seconds to 7 minutes and 20 seconds (average duration of 4 minutes and 10 seconds). A validation set is also defined and conformed by 5 excerpts of 20 seconds randomly chosen from the training data.

Huang et al. [2014a] best results were achieved using a deep recurrent architecture based on 3 hidden layers where the second is recurrent. Each hidden layer has 1000 units characterized by a RELU non-linear function, the output layer is a linear layer modelling two sources (see Figure 3.1): denoted as $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{1t}$ (target: vocals) and $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{2t}$ (other: background instruments). Moreover, they jointly optimized the net with a time-frequency mask:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{1t} = \frac{|\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{1t}|}{|\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{1t}| + |\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{2t}|} \odot \mathbf{z}_t$$

attached after the output layer. Thus, enforces the constraint that the sum of the predictions is equal to the original mixture. \mathbf{z}_t refers to the input spectra at frame t . Where \odot denotes element-wise matrix multiplication and $|\cdot|$ means the absolute value.

The input audio waves are normalized such that the target to separate (vocals) and the background instruments have energy one, respectively. Furthermore, the mix from where the sources are estimated is created by adding the normalized input waves. One can argue that this mixing is rather artificial but is chosen for two reasons: first, because after aural inspection the mix seems reasonable and second, because a normalization is needed and Huang et al. [2014a] did it in that way.

²<https://github.com/posenhuang/deeplearningsourceseparation>

³<http://sisec.inria.fr/professionally-produced-music-recordings/>

FIGURE 3.1: Baseline DRNN architecture based on the work published by Huang et al. [2014a].

A context window of 3 frames ($|\mathbf{z}_{t-1}|$, $|\mathbf{z}_t|$ and $|\mathbf{z}_{t+1}|$) of the magnitude spectra composes the input vector (\mathbf{x}_t) of the net. A raised $\sin()$ of size 1024 is used as analysis window with FFT size of 1024 and 50% overlapping.

Another successful proposal of Huang et al. [2014a] was to introduce a discriminative training cost characterized by a gamma parameter ($\gamma=0.05$) together with the Mean Squared Error (MSE) cost function:

$$J_{MSE\,disc} = \|\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{1t} - \mathbf{y}_{1t}\|_2^2 - \gamma\|\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{1t} - \mathbf{y}_{2t}\|_2^2 + \|\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{2t} - \mathbf{y}_{2t}\|_2^2 - \gamma\|\tilde{\mathbf{y}}_{2t} - \mathbf{y}_{1t}\|_2^2$$

This cost function tries to decrease the similarity between the prediction and the targets of other sources, not only to increase the similarity between target and prediction of the same source.

The model is optimized by back-propagating the gradients with respect to the training objectives. The L-BFGS algorithm is used to train the models from normalized random initialization. Feedforward connections are initialized randomly with the initialization scheme proposed by Glorot and Bengio [2010], with the following uniform distribution:

$$U\left(-\sqrt{\frac{6}{n_{in} + n_{out}}}, \sqrt{\frac{6}{n_{in} + n_{out}}}\right)$$

n_{in} refers to the number of hidden neurons in the *previous* layer and n_{out} refers to the number of hidden neurons in the *forthcoming* layer.

The recurrent connections are initialized with the initialization scheme proposed by [Glorot and Bengio \[2010\]](#) but smaller:

$$U\left(-\sqrt{\frac{6}{3 \cdot n_{in}}}, \sqrt{\frac{6}{3 \cdot n_{in}}}\right)$$

Bias weights are initialized to zero. This initialization is the one proposed by default in [Huang et al. \[2014a\]](#) code.

No formal justification for the recurrent connections initialization was found, those are described as in the code are. But the fact that the recurrent connections are initialized to a smaller value than the feedforward connections could be to avoid gradient explode problems since no strategies are used to avoid such problems inherent in RNNs.

The maximum epoch is set to 500 and the best model is selected according to the validation set. Experiments with long runs have shown that 500 epochs are enough to find a proper model since most of the improvement during training is achieved among the first 500 iterations.

3.2.1.1 Results

-	Target (vocals)			Other (background)		
Song	SDR	SIR	SAR	SDR	SIR	SAR
Befo	0.930167	2.790987	7.343461	0.149388	1.531111	8.107453
Dock	4.903680	6.990222	9.880558	4.740333	7.525816	8.694657
Hall	0.522228	0.876418	14.177771	1.314991	5.175269	4.766591
Jud2	6.919158	11.391774	9.141740	6.212215	8.657343	10.427051
Jude	9.992370	14.850751	11.850206	8.113411	9.991163	13.074703
Mic2	6.069313	7.323037	12.814931	9.250029	17.393467	10.051375
Global	5.515843	8.302270	10.557432	5.585666	9.051546	9.594718
Processing time	2min 58.2sec (source separation) + 2min (evaluation)					

TABLE 3.3: DRNN baseline: BSS Eval results.

3.2.2 DRNN experiments

This section experiments with several deep and recurrent architectures:

- **DRNN2**: 3 hidden layers where the 2nd is recurrent,
- **DRNN3**: 3 hidden layers where the 3rd is recurrent,
- **DRNN4**: 4 hidden layers where the 3rd is recurrent,
- **DNN3**: 3 hidden layers with no recurrent connections,
- **DNN4**: 4 hidden layers with no recurrent connections,

and also with several initialization schemes for the recurrent connections are proposed to study how:

- **initHe-1**: small values initialization work,
- **initHe-0.1**: initialization with even smaller values work (to avoid gradient explode problems),
- **initHe-10**: initialization with bigger values work (to avoid gradient vanish problems),
- **IRNN**: IRNN behaves,
- **IRNN-0.1**: attenuated IRNN work,
- **IRNN-0.01**: attenuated IRNN work.

Where the initializations are denoted as follows: *initScheme-multiplicativeFactor*. Two *initScheme* are considered: **initHe**, referring to the scheme proposed by He et al. [2015], and **IRNN**, referring to the Identity RNN of Le et al. [2015] (for further information about these methods see Chapter 2.2.3). The *multiplicativeFactor* is applied a posteriori to the initialization scheme. For example, IRNN may be the identity matrix with ones; but when considering IRNN-0.01 the identity matrix is multiplied by 0.01, getting an identity matrix of 0.01.

The bias terms are initialized to be zero and the feedforward connections are initialized considering the scheme proposed by He et al. [2015]. All other parameters that are not detailed here (cost function, joint optimization with the time-frequency mask, etc.) are set equally as in the baseline implementation introduced before.

All combinations of architecture and initializations are tested in order to see the benefits of each design parameter when using DRNN for the audio source separation task.

Remember that the goal in this section is to study how theoretically motivated \mathbf{W}_{rec} initializations behave compared to the baseline DRNN that does not deal with the problems inherent in DRNN (gradient vanish/explode). Hopefully those initializations are more appropriate and we can improve the results reported by Huang et al. [2014a].

3.2.2.1 Results

The following tables are computed using the same random seed for Matlab; therefore: although the initializations is *random*, is the same for all the schemes and configurations.

Tables 3.4 and 3.5 show the global SDR for the test dataset. Remember the meaning of global: the mean weighted by the length of the songs.

	DRNN2		DRNN3		DRNN4	
	init	SDR	init	SDR	init	SDR
1.	initHe-1	5.5741	initHe-1	5.5337	IRNN-0.1	5.3437
2.	IRNN-0.01	5.4137	IRNN-0.1	5.3041	initHe-0.1	5.1937
3.	IRNN-0.1	5.3440	initHe-0.1	5.2849	initHe-1	5.1837
4.	initHe-0.1	5.3318	IRNN-0.01	5.1699	IRNN-0.01	5.1788
5.	IRNN	4.4026	IRNN	4.3729	IRNN	3.8505
6.	initHe-10	NaN	initHe-10	NaN	initHe-10	NaN

TABLE 3.4: DRNN results: fixing recurrent architecture.

	initHe-1		initHe-0.1		initHe-10		IRNN		IRNN-0.1		IRNN-0.01	
	D	S	D	S	D	S	D	S	D	S	D	S
	R	N	R	N	R	N	R	N	R	N	R	N
	N	R	N	R	N	R	N	R	N	R	N	R
1.	2	5.5741	2	5.3318	2	NaN	2	4.4026	2	5.3440	2	5.4137
2.	3	5.5337	3	5.2849	3	NaN	3	4.3729	4	5.3437	4	5.1788
3.	4	5.1837	4	5.1937	4	NaN	4	3.8505	3	5.3041	3	5.1699

TABLE 3.5: DRNN results: fixing recurrent initialization. The DRNN column refers to the recurrent architecture names: DRNN2, DRNN3 and DRNN4.

When using `initHe-10` initialization the results are always *NaN*'s. This is due to a bad W_{rec} initialization: weights are too big and generate big outputs that end up with sound instabilities that produce *NaN*'s when evaluating the song with the BSS Eval script. This result denotes the importance of a good initialization, is important to initialize the weights such that generate output activations close to the data range.

Results are not that good when using IRNN because our model do not requires very long temporal dependencies. But when forcing the model not to learn long temporal dependencies (attenuating IRNN), DRNN perform as well as others. This behave was also described by [Le et al. \[2015\]](#).

Is interesting to see that even introducing more layers (as in DRNN4), results do not improve. Is plausible to say that, when we introduce more layers, our model suffers overfitting because we are training a model with more parameters but with the same data. In general, one can observe how: DRNN2 model outperforms other architectures (with this amount of training data) and that `initHe-1` is the most successful initialization. However, if the initial weights allow the output activations to be inside the data range, the choice of the initialization is not crucial because the difference in performance is rather small.

Table 3.6 compares different architectures with its own best recurrent initializations and with `initHe` initialization for the feedforward connections (as was originally proposed by [He et al. \[2015\]](#)). Randomness is generated with the same Matlab seed as before, to be able to compare results. Note that DNNs do not require a recurrent initialization; then, this field is empty in the table (denoted by -).

Arch./Best W_{rec} init.	Target (vocals)			Other (background)		
	SDR	SIR	SAR	SDR	SIR	SAR
DNN3/ -	5.3935	7.7366	11.0878	5.4649	8.4062	10.1516
DNN4/ -	5.1661	7.2546	11.3599	5.4041	8.2632	10.0633
DRNN2/ <code>initHe-1</code>	5.5741	8.4182	10.6996	5.5367	8.7082	10.0786
DRNN3/ <code>initHe-1</code>	5.5337	8.1318	10.8036	5.6497	8.7708	10.0104
DRNN4/IRNN-0.1	5.3437	7.5567	11.2398	5.6147	8.5877	10.1833

TABLE 3.6: Comparing different deep and recurrent architectures.

Previous researchers reported similar results in the sense that deep-recurrent structures perform better than deep structures [[Huang et al., 2014a](#)] for the audio source separation task.

The best model is DRNN2/initHe-1 with the following scores for each song:

-	Target (vocals)			Other (background)		
Song	SDR	SIR	SAR	SDR	SIR	SAR
Befo	0.727	2.588	7.212	-0.015	1.234	8.444
Dock	4.941	6.864	10.219	4.719	7.145	9.170
Hall	0.580	0.804	16.197	2.031	4.647	6.755
Jud2	6.839	11.571	8.913	5.687	7.639	10.790
Jude	9.904	14.735	11.779	7.927	9.706	13.103
Mic2	6.639	8.096	12.715	9.698	18.134	10.436
Global	5.5741	8.4182	10.6996	5.5367	8.7082	10.0786
Processing time	1min 49.63sec (source separation) + 2min (evaluation)					

TABLE 3.7: Best DRNN results, achieved with the model: DRNN2/initHe-1.

3.2.3 Discussion

3.2.3.1 DRNN

We can observe that the baseline DRNN results (with Glorot and Bengio [2010] initialization scheme, in Table 3.3) and the experimental results (with W_{rec} initializations theoretically motivated, in Table 3.7) are similar. If the initialization allows the output activations to be inside the data range (during the first iteration before back-propagating), the model is able to find a good solution. Note that both, Glorot and Bengio [2010] and He et al. [2015], initialization schemes try to keep the variance in a controlled range. Those methods do exactly what we want: to control the output activations to be inside a reasonable range (the data range).

Like Huang et al. [2014a], we also concluded that the architecture that provides better performance is DRNN2.

We did not encounter any problem of gradient vanishing nor explode. Temporal dependencies exist because better performance is achieved using DRNN than DNN, but they are rather sort. That is the reason why our models do not suffer problems of gradient vanish/explode inherent in DRNN nets, because they do not need long-term memory. We can observe that no long-term memory is needed when attenuated IRNN outperform IRNN. This long-term memory issue relates with (same as equation 2.39):

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}_{(t)}^{(1)}}{\partial \mathbf{h}_{(k)}^{(1)}} \right\| \leq (\gamma_{W_{rec}} \gamma_{\sigma})^{(t-k)} \quad (3.1)$$

meaning that if the gradient vanishes or explodes the input at stage k , such state does not influence the output at stage t ; then the information from the long past would not help. But, since the temporal dependency is rather short: this is not a problem.

Also remember that the provided input vector does not only contain the current frame, but also the neighboring frames. The net considers also this past and future input, instead of paying only attention into the recurrent feed. This can be an explanation why not much memory is required for our models.

These could be the reasons why [Huang et al. \[2014a\]](#), [Maas et al. \[2012\]](#) nor us did not suffer gradient vanish/explode problems even that they did not address this issue explicitly.

L-BFGS is used for training the models. Recently, a second order method (Hessian-Free optimization method) has produced some impressive results [[Martens, 2010](#)]. Similarly: the fact of using L-BFGS, a second order method, favors to find a better local minima choosing better directions along plateaus. Then, a reasonable enough initialization together with an efficient optimization method (L-BFGS) allows the model to get a local minima with good generalization properties. That could be one more reason why [Huang et al. \[2014a\]](#) and [Maas et al. \[2012\]](#) got such impressive results.

3.3 Discussion: FASST-NMF vs. DRNN

In Table 3.8 one can observe that DRNN is a competitive model since similar SDR performance when separating the target is achieved in comparison to FASST-NMF. Moreover, DRNN reduces drastically the long run time of FASST-NMF.

-	Target (vocals)			Other (background)			Time
	SDR	SIR	SAR	SDR	SIR	SAR	
FASST-NMF	5.9914	26.6353	6.1211	9.9288	11.6723	15.4332	4h 39m
DRNN best init.	5.5741	8.4182	10.6996	5.5367	8.7082	10.0786	1m 49s
DRNN baseline	5.5158	8.3022	10.5574	5.5856	9.0515	9.5947	2m 58s

TABLE 3.8: Comparing FASST vs. DRNN.

SAR performance for the target is better with DRNN than with FASST-NMF. But one can observe that FASST outperforms DRNN for SIR measures. This is because FASST can exploit panning information (stereo inputs are allowed) and DRNN operates with mono signals.

But when comparing the songs individually in Tables 3.2, 3.3 and 3.7 one can observe that DRNN models achieve lower performance for Befo and Hall songs than for the rest songs; while with the FASST algorithm results are more uniform through all songs. After checking Table 4.6, one realizes that Befo and Hall songs are the only ones having two sources: vocals + guitar/piano. The bad performance achieved for these songs is probably due to the fact that in the training database there are not many songs with such characteristics; mainly, it is composed of songs played by a full band. This denotes the importance of training with a database close to the kind of music that one wishes to separate.

Chapter 4

Perceptual Experiments

The here proposed experiments are based on the methodology used in [Buyens et al. \[2014\]](#), where the music mixing preferences of CI users are studied. Two perceptual experiments are conducted: Experiment 1 is designed to explore which mixings are preferred for CIs; Experiment 2 assesses generally if those are appropriate.

Subjects have no time constraints for doing each experiment. Patients can take a break whenever is necessary. Subjects signed a consent form and were paid for their travel expenses. Ethical committee approval was obtained.

The audio is sent through a loudspeaker (Genelec 8240 APM) into an acoustically treated room. For patients with residual hearing the sound is sent through a cable connected to their processor. As different brands of CIs are tested, patients are asked to use a common speech program (instead of music program, for example) to avoid more variability. If the patient has two implants, he/she is asked to keep the one giving best performance.

FIGURE 4.1: *Perceptual experiments setup.*

ID	Subject	Age	Gender	CI experience (years)	Etiology	Sound processor	Implant type	Brand
BSS001-012	S1	79	Male	13	Sudden hearing loss	CP810	Nucleus CI24R (CS) (Left)	Cochlear
BSS002	S2	62	Male	8	Otosclerosis	Freedom	Nucleus CI24RE (CS) (Left)	Cochlear
BSS003-020	S3	66	Male	7	Genetics	Opus2	Sonata ti100 (Left)	MEDEL
BSS004	S1	54	Male	3	Unknown	Opus2	ConcertoFlex EAS 24 (Left)	MEDEL
BSS005	S5	50	Male	14	Sudden hearing loss	Harmony	Clarion CII (Left)	AB
BSS009	S6	66	Male	2	Sudden hearing loss	CP810	Nucleus CI24RE (CA) (Left)	MEDEL
BSS010	S7	73	Male	4	Unknown	CP810	CI512 (Left)	Cochlear
BSS011	S8	60	Male	6	Unknown	Naida	HIRE90k (Left)	AB
BSS013	S9	56	Female	7	Sudden hearing loss	CP910	Nucleus CI24RE (CA) (Left)	Cochlear
BSS014	S10	47	Female	19	Ototoxic	Harmony	Clarion (Right)	AB
BSS021	S11	67	Female	4	Sudden hearing loss	CP910	Nucleus CI24RE (CA) (Left)	Cochlear
BSS023	S12	67	Female	6	Sudden hearing loss	Naida	HIRE90k (Right)	AB

TABLE 4.1: *CI users profiles.*

Subject	Gender	Age	Subject	Gender	Age
NH1	Male	32	NH6	Female	26
NH2	Male	30	NH7	Male	41
NH3	Male	40	NH8	Male	34
NH4	Female	25	NH9	Male	40
NH5	Female	32			

TABLE 4.2: *NH listeners profiles.*

All music excerpts were presented at 60dB(A); a comfort level below 65 dB(A), the threshold from where CI devices start applying automatic gain control. The different loudness (computed with the ReplayGain standard [Robinson, 2001]) levels between songs was compensated applying the corresponding gain distributively to the tracks, keeping the NH mix intact.

Table 4.1 shows the profiles of the subjects that participated in the study. Five post-lingual CI subjects (S1-S5) participated in Experiment 1, nine post-lingual CI subjects (S1,S3 and S6-12) participated in Experiment 2 and nine NH subjects (NH1-NH9) participated in Experiment 2.

4.1 Design Experiment 1

4.1.1 Motivation

This experiment allows CI users to determine the most enjoyable mix given a multitrack source and a mixing console. The goal is to derive some mixing pre-sets potentially more enjoyable for CI users than regular NH mixes.

Two kinds of music are presented during Experiment 1: popular music and orchestral music. For the former music style the multitrack is presented in its original form or estimated using SS. Thus, would allow us to observe the effects of the SS algorithms into the music mixing preferences of implantees. For the latter music style, the goal is to find (if any) the mixing pre-sets that potentially are more enjoyable for CI users than regular NH mixes.

4.1.2 Methods

Two different configurations of background instruments are considered. For popular music: two mix channels (2 tracks: vocals and instruments) and three mix channels (3 tracks: vocals, bass/drums and others). And for orchestral music: two mix channels (2 tracks: melody and background instruments) and three mix channels (3 tracks: melody, percussion and background instruments).

Two different tracks configurations for: the orchestral multitrack, the popular multitrack and the popular estimated multitrack are presented 10 times in random order (2 configurations x 3 songs x 10 times = 60 test repetitions).

Five post-lingual CI subjects are asked to determine the most enjoyable audio mix by adjusting the gains of the multitrack sounds in a mixing console that remains playing in an infinite loop. The mixing console is a Web App, available on GitHub¹: it is a fork of an online multitrack player called MT5² created by Buffa et al.. It is programmed in HTML5, JavaScript and Web Audio API³.

FIGURE 4.2: *Experiment 1 GUI. A modified version of MT5: a multitrack mixer for the browser.*

Initially, all track sliders are placed in down position in order to avoid suggesting *a priori* mixing preferences. Moreover, the tracks are presented as Track1, Track2 and Track3 (without any additional information about the source); doing so, the user is forced to listen the tracks to know which instruments are present in each. The user is suggested to listen to each track separately before starting the test.

The gain dynamic range (from -70dB to 0) of the sliders is kept small to allow the subjects to have enough precision when moving the slider. Sliders lowest value is -70dB because the subject should be able to attenuate completely a track and the maximum value allowed is 0dB to avoid saturating (clipping) the signal. Additionally, to ensure that subjects do not use visual cues during the test a random offset gain is added independently to each track (within a range from -15dB to 0dB, to allow enough variety between test songs). Some questions were asked to gather the musicological background of the subject:

¹<https://github.com/jordipons/MT5>

²<http://mt5demo.gexsoft.com/>

³<https://dvcs.w3.org/hg/audio/raw-file/tip/webaudio/specification.html>

- Level of knowledge about classical music? From 1-10.
- Level of knowledge about popular modern music? From 1-10.

The experiment was conformed by two parts: train (10 trials) and test (60 trials). A detailed schedule of the experiment is attached in Appendix A (the checklist used during the experiments).

The volume was adjusted so that the loudspeaker produces 60dB(A) with all the sliders at -30dB position. CI subjects are advised that the comfort level is adjusted to be around the -30dB position of the sliders, increasing a lot the volume can be too loud for them.

The following acoustic material was used:

- Pop multitrack: tests for popular music tests are carried out with the same song that [Buyens et al. \[2014\]](#) used: *Dock of the Bay by Otis Redding*. Where the most common instruments in pop bands are present: vocals, piano, guitar, bass guitar and drums. All instruments (including voice) are present homogeneously.
- Pop estimated multitrack (SS): the same pop song, *Dock of the Bay by Otis Redding*, was mixed and further decomposed by the FASST algorithm. The audio tracks were normalized to produce a similar loudness than the original multitracks using ReplayGain [[Robinson, 2001](#)]. Each of the estimated tracks were normalized to have the same loudness (ReplayGain) than the original tracks.
- Classical multitrack: an excerpt from *Alex The Adventurer by Jeffrey Hayat* was chosen for its clear rhythm/beat. The song is free available online ⁴.

Tables [4.6](#) and [4.8](#) show more details about the characteristics of each song.

4.1.3 Results

Results obtained from the resulting gains of the mixing console after the experiments are presented in dB relative to vocals (for popular music) or in dB relative to main melody (for orchestral music). One can note this way of presenting the results in Figures [4.3](#),

⁴<http://www.cambridge-mt.com/ms-mtk.htm>

4.4 and 4.5, where 0dBs level corresponds to vocals/main melody level. The rows of these figures correspond to the track configurations (two mix channels, first row, and three mix channels, second row) and the columns represent each CI user. One can also observe how values of B/D (Bass/Drums) and P/G (Piano/Guitar) in the first row of Figure 4.3 and 4.4 (representing the two mix channels configuration) are the same, because under this configuration B/D and P/G are forming together a track. Similarly is expressed in the first row of Figure 4.5, where the values of Perc. (percussion) and Accomp. (accompaniment) move together.

4.1.3.1 Statistical analysis

Differences in level settings between tracks were analyzed with the Wilcoxon signed-ranks test with Bonferroni correction. Wilcoxon signed-ranks test is a non-parametric (when the population is so small that one cannot assume a gaussian distribution) statistical hypothesis test used when comparing two related samples. In Experiment 1 each test is repeated 10 times. The Wilcoxon signed-ranks test is used to check if the distribution of the values of different sliders are significantly different. Bonferroni correction is a method used to counteract the problem of multiple comparisons. When increase the number of hypotheses being tested into the same data, the likelihood of a rare event also increases together with the likelihood of incorrectly rejecting a null hypothesis. To avoid such situation, Bonferroni correction proposes to test each individual hypothesis at a statistical significance alpha level $\alpha = 0.05/m$; what it would be equivalent if only one hypothesis was tested (being m the number of hypothesis tested).

4.1.3.2 Popular Music

The goal here is to observe whether the artifacts/errors produced by the SS algorithm affect the mixing preferences. For doing so, the results obtained using the original multitrack are compared to the ones obtained using the estimated multitrack. Individual results using the original multitrack and using the estimated multitrack are presented in Figures 4.3 and 4.4 respectively.

Subjects were asked to determine their own level of knowledge about popular modern music (from 1-10): S1-3, S2-4, S3-8, S4-5 and S5-7.

Comparing the two mix channels configuration results

In the configuration with two mix channels for the original multitrack recording (top row in Figure 4.3), the preferred vocal level is set significantly higher than the instruments level when averaging for all subjects (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .003) with a vocals-to-instruments ratio mean value of 1.92 dB.

Regarding the estimated multitrack for the two mix channels (top row in Figure 4.4), the vocals level is set significantly higher than the instruments level when averaging for all subjects (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = 7.393e-07) with a vocals-to-instruments ratio mean value of 3.82 dB.

Comparing the three mix channels configuration results

In the configuration with three mix channels for the original multitrack recording (bottom row in Figure 4.3), the preferred vocal level is set higher than the P/G level when averaging for all subjects (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: **p-value = .007**); with a vocals-to-P/G ratio mean value of 2.36 dB.

Regarding the estimated multitrack for the three mix channels (bottom row in Figure 4.4), the preferred vocal level is set higher than the P/G level when averaging for all subjects (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = **2.051e-05**) with a vocals-to-P/G ratio mean value of 1.72 dB. The vocal level is also set higher than the B/D level when averaging for all subjects (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .025) with a vocals-to-B/D ratio mean value of 3.2 dB.

In the configuration with three mix channels for the original multitrack recording (bottom row in Figure 4.3), the preferred vocal level is set higher than the B/D level for S3 (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: **p-value = .009**); however, S4 preferred the B/D level set higher than the vocals (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .023), with a vocals-to-B/D ratio mean value of 4.7 dB and -3.3 dB, respectively. The vocal level is also set higher than the P/G level for subjects: S2 (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: **p-value = .014**) and S3 (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .037); with a vocals-to-P/G ratio mean value of 5.8 dB and 3 dB, respectively. The B/D level is also set higher than the P/G level for S5 (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .021) with a B/D-to-P/G ratio mean value of 1.8 dB.

FIGURE 4.3: *Results for the original popular music multitrack. Individual level settings for CI subjects S1 – S5 (represented in columns) are shown in two configurations: two mix channels (top row) and three mix channels (bottom row).*

FIGURE 4.4: *Results for the estimated popular music multitrack. Individual level settings for CI subjects S1 – S5 (represented in columns) are shown in two configurations: two mix channels (top row) and three mix channels (bottom row).*

Regarding the estimated multitrack for the three mix channels (bottom row in Figure 4.4), the preferred vocal level is set higher than the P/G level for subjects: S2 (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .037), S3 (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: **p-value = .016**) and S5 (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .023); with a vocals-to-P/G ratio mean value of 3.1 dB, 3.6 dB and 4.1 dB, respectively. The B/D level is also set higher than the P/G level for S5 (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .009) with a B/D-to-P/G ratio mean value of 4.9 dB.

Results with p-value > 0.05 are not included into that section. After **Bonferroni correction** ($m = 3$; $\alpha = 0.0167$), only results in **bold are significant**.

4.1.3.3 **Orchestral Music**

Subjects were asked to determine their own level of knowledge about classical music (from 1-10): S1-**6**, S2-**5**, S3-**7**, S4-**8** and S5-**4**.

Comparing the two mix channels configuration results

In the configuration with two mix channels (top row in Figure 4.5) for subjects with a level of knowledge about classical music > 5, the main melody is set higher than the background instruments (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: **p-value = .001**) with a melody-to-background ratio mean value of 4.43 dB.

Results with a significant difference p-value > 0.05 are not included in this section. After **Bonferroni correction** ($m = 2$; $\alpha = 0.025$), only results in **bold are significant**.

Therefore, no significant difference was found (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .23) for subjects with a level of knowledge on classical music < 5.

Comparing the three mix channels configuration results

In the configuration with three mix channels (bottom row in Figure 4.5) for subjects with a level of knowledge about classical music > 5, the preferred percussion section level is set lower than the main melody level (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .010) with a melody-to-percussion ratio mean value of 4.03 dB. The percussion level is also set lower than the accompaniment level (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: p-value = .009) with a percussion-to-accompaniment ratio mean value of -3.73 dB.

In the configuration with three mix channels (bottom row in Figure 4.5) for subjects with a level of knowledge about classical music < 5 , the preferred percussion section level is set higher than the main melody level (Wilcoxon signed-ranks test: **p-value = .002**) with a melody-to-percussion ratio mean value of -4.35 dB.

Results with a significant difference p-value > 0.05 are not included into that section. After **Bonferroni correction** ($m = 6$; $\alpha = 0.0083$), only results in **bold** are significant.

FIGURE 4.5: *Results for the orchestral music multitrack. Individual level settings for CI subjects S1 – S5 (represented in columns) are shown in two configurations: two mix channels (top row) and three mix channels (bottom row).*

4.1.4 Discussion

4.1.4.1 Popular Music

Comparing the two mix channels configuration results

One can observe that for both, original multitrack and estimated multitrack, the mixing preferences are similar. In both cases the vocal level is set significantly higher than the instruments level, what agrees with the findings published by [Buyens et al. \[2014\]](#).

Considering those results, the following mixing pre-sets are proposed for Experiment 2 (where the effects of the SS are further studied by means of a pairwise comparison).

Mixing pre-set	Voice	Bass/drums	Others
<i>Standard</i>	0dB	0dB	0dB
<i>-6dB</i>	0dB	-6dB	-6dB
<i>-12dB</i>	0dB	-12dB	-12dB

TABLE 4.3: *SS-Pop music mixing pre-sets.*

Standard is formed by adding the tracks, which is assumed to represent a mix for NH. In *-6dB* and *-12dB* conditions the background instruments are attenuated 6 dB and 12 dB, respectively. One could argue that the *-12dB* mixing pre-set is artificial since this is far away from the mean values observed into the gathered data (vocals-to-instruments ratio: 1.92dB and 3.82dB). This condition is added to force an extreme mix where the artifacts introduced by the SS can be perceived (at least for NH).

Comparing the three mix channels configuration results

One can observe that for both, original multitrack and estimated multitrack, the mixing preferences are similar. In both cases there the P/G level is set significantly lower than the vocals, what agrees with the findings published by [Buyens et al. \[2014\]](#) where they show a preference for mixings with the harmonic part (P/G) attenuated.

The unique significant difference between the original multitrack and the estimated is observed for S3. Where the B/D level is set significantly higher than the vocals for the original multitrack; this preference for the rhythm/beat is also described in the literature [[Gfeller et al., 2010](#); [Buyens et al., 2014](#)].

This three mix channels information is important to re-validate the results from [Buyens et al. \[2014\]](#) but those results are not going to be further used. Our research question is not about CI users mixing preferences, our goal is to study the effects of the SS. The effects of the SS are studied in a two mix channels configuration to avoid a big amount of comparisons and simplify the study and its conclusions.

4.1.4.2 **Orchestral Music**

Experiment 1 goal is to propose mixing pre-sets more suitable for CI users rather than common NH ones. Regarding the strongest differences between track levels, the mixing

pre-sets detailed in Table 4.4 are proposed.

Mixing pre-set	Main melody	Percussion	Accomp.
<i>Standard</i>	0dB	0dB	0dB
<i>-6dB</i>	0dB	-6dB	-6dB
<i>-12dB</i>	0dB	-12dB	-12dB
<i>Details</i>	0dB	-6dB	-3dB
	Beat	NObeat	
<i>Beat6</i>	0dB	-6dB	
<i>Beat12</i>	0dB	-12dB	

TABLE 4.4: *Orchestral music mixing pre-sets.*

Standard is formed by adding the tracks, which is assumed to represent a mix for NH. Furthermore, this mix seems also suitable for non experienced CI users (as we can observe in Figure 4.5). *-6dB* and *-12dB* conditions are proposed since there is a significant preference for a clear main melody and attenuated background instruments. *Beat6* and *Beat12* picks the significant preference for the percussion section (beat). Instrument tracks responsible for beat are grouped (manually) into the beat section and the remaining instruments (main melody and further musical details) are grouped into the NObeat section. NObeat is attenuated to favor the beat encoding. *Details* is proposed after observing a preference (not significant) for an attenuated percussion section (lower than the melody and also lower than the accompaniment). This mixing pre-set attenuates the percussion section to reduce the beat information to show up the musical details bad encoded by CIs (allowing them to be better encoded).

It is also interesting to observe how listening to music (training) helps to improve musicological understanding; subjects with a higher level of classical music knowledge listen more often to music [Gfeller et al., 2003; Nogueira et al., 2011]. If subjects are divided into two groups of expertise (above/below 5): patients with a level of knowledge < 5 prefer a higher percussion section level than the main melody (showing a significant preference for beat), while patients with a level of knowledge > 5 show a preference for higher accompaniment levels and attenuated percussion (showing more interest for musicological details than beat). This behavior is also going to be studied in Experiment 2, where it is expected a preference for clear beat mixes for non-expert CI classical music listeners and a preference for attenuated beat mixes for expert CI classical music listeners.

4.2 Design Experiment 2

4.2.1 Motivation

Experiment 2 is divided into two independent parts (popular music test and orchestral music test) to answer the two previously posed research questions:

- Do CI users perceive the error/artifacts produced by the non-perfect estimation of the multitrack? (using state of the art SS techniques over popular music)
- Do CI users enjoy better orchestral music given a different mixing setup than NH listeners?

4.2.2 Methods

Before starting the experiment, the subject is trained to perform the task. The training phase consisted on 12 comparisons (6 with popular music and 6 with classical music).

The first part of Experiment 2, the popular music test, is meant to answer the first question related to pop music and SS. Based on the results gathered in Experiment 1 (Table 4.3), different mixing pre-sets pairs are defined (Table 4.5) in order to assess whether the artifacts/errors produced by the SS algorithm are perceived or not. A pairwise comparison test is used. A preference question based on which music excerpt (song A or B) produces a more enjoyable sensation is used. The order of the mixing pre-set assigned to song A or B was randomized.

Song A	Song B
<i>-6dBSS</i>	<i>-6dBMT</i>
<i>-12dBMT</i>	<i>-12dBSS</i>
<i>Standard</i>	<i>-6dBSS</i>
<i>-6dBMT</i>	<i>Standard</i>
<i>Standard</i>	<i>-12dBSS</i>
<i>-12dBMT</i>	<i>Standard</i>

TABLE 4.5: *Experiment 2 pairs for the SS study.*

The estimated and the original multitrack are denoted here as *mixSS* and *mixMT* respectively. One can note that the pairs are defined to see the effects of the SS: comparing the same mixing pre-set with different multitrack sources (original and estimated) and

trying to see if the mixing preferences change when using the SS algorithm (comparing the $-6dB$ and $-12dB$ mixing pre-sets w.r.t. *Standard*).

Pairs are randomly presented three times for each song listed in Table 4.6 (6 songs x 6 pairs x 3 repetitions = 108 pairs). No classical music is involved here, orchestral music is going to be studied in the second part of the experiment.

ID	Song	V	P	G	B	D
<i>Hal</i>	<i>Hallelujah (Leonard Cohen)</i>	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Bef</i>	<i>Before I Go (Papermouth)</i>	+	-	+	-	-
<i>Mic2</i>	<i>Michel (Anouk)</i>	+	-	+	+	-
<i>Jud2</i>	<i>Hey Jude (excerpt A) (The Beatles)</i>	+	-	+	+	-
<i>Jude</i>	<i>Hey Jude (excerpt B) (The Beatles)</i>	+	-	+	+	+
<i>Dock</i>	<i>Dock of the Bay (Otis Redding)</i>	+	+	+	+	+

TABLE 4.6: *Popular music excerpts used for Experiment 2.*

The multitrack recordings used for the popular music study were kindly shared by Wim Buyens; those are the same he used for his study [Buyens et al., 2014]. This would allow us to compare the results.

The second research question, where CI users orchestral music mixing preferences are studied, is answered in the second part of the experiment (orchestral test). The mixing pre-sets defined in Table 4.4 are considered; all mixing pre-sets are compared with respect to the *Standard* condition three times for each song presented in random order (5 pairs x 5 songs x 3 repetitions = 90 pairs). Table 4.7 shows the tested pairs and Table 4.8 describe the orchestral songs. The order of the excerpts assigned to song A or B was randomized.

Song A	Song B
<i>Standard</i>	$-6dB$
<i>Details</i>	<i>Standard</i>
<i>Standard</i>	<i>Beat6</i>
<i>Beat12</i>	<i>Standard</i>
<i>Standard</i>	$-12dB$

TABLE 4.7: *Experiment 2 pairs for the orchestral study.*

Alex the Adventurer is downloaded from *The 'Mixing Secrets' Free Multitrack Download Library*⁵. The remaining multitrack recordings were kindly shared by Tapio Lokki. They recorded a symphony orchestra in an anechoic chamber (for further details see: Pätynen et al. [2008]); the audios are free available for academic use.

⁵<http://www.cambridge-mt.com/ms-mtk.htm>

Song	Melody	Beat	Other
<i>Alex the Adventurer</i>	Strings and Percussion	Percussion and Brass	Strings
<i>Beethoven</i>	Strings	Percussion and Brass	Woodwinds
<i>Bruckner</i>	Woodwinds	Percussion and Brass	Strings
<i>Mahler (excerpt 1)</i>	Strings and Woodwinds	Percussion and Brass	-
<i>Mahler (excerpt 2)</i>	Strings and Woodwinds	Percussion and Brass	-
<i>Mahler (excerpt 3)</i>	Strings and Woodwinds	Percussion and Brass	-

TABLE 4.8: *Orchestral music excerpts used for Experiment 2.*

One can note that the audio excerpts used in Experiment 1 are also introduced as part of Experiment 2 (as [Buyens et al. \[2014\]](#) did).

Each subject was asked to choose the most enjoyable song between A and B. Subjects were advised that there were no good or bad answers. Figure 4.6 shows the Web App programmed in HTML5 that was used to conduct the experiment.

FIGURE 4.6: *Experiment 2 GUI. Subjects can listen and choose which song do they enjoy most.*

In order to allow the users to compare efficiently songs A and B they were told to listen between 3 and 5 seconds of each song. We encouraged them to keep following that strategy until they were confident about their decision. This strategy is interesting for two reasons: to save spending useless time comparing two songs (when the user has already a clear preference) and to facilitate the task since it is more easy to compare (to memorize) short audio intervals than long songs.

Different loudness levels (measured as ReplayGain [[Robinson, 2001](#)]) between songs was compensated applying the corresponding gain distributively to the tracks, keeping the NH mix intact. But for generating the other mixes, only the background is attenuated

(*i.e.* 6dB or 12dB) setting as reference points with similar loudness the voice (for the popular test) or the main melody/beat (for the orchestral test). Remember that those are not attenuated: in Tables 4.4 and 4.3 one can observe that are set to 0dB. But the background instruments have different levels of loudness after being remixed. One could argue that this strategy can be problematic since then songs A and B have different loudness levels, but this is the unique way we found to keep an absolute difference (*i.e.* 6dB) between the different tracks among songs and then be able to compare results to find conclusions.

9 post-lingual CI subjects participated in the study. Furthermore, 9 NH subjects also participated in the study asses whether the *Standard* condition is preferred by NHs. To ensure that there is no bias into our test due to the assumption that the *Standard* condition represents the mix for NH listeners and also to compare the mixing preferences of CI users vs. NH listeners.

The preference score between mix A and B is indicated in percentages computed dividing the preference frequency for A or B by the total number of comparisons. A and B are complementary.

Finally, subjects are asked if they usually listen to popular/classical music. Further details about the schedule of Experiment 2 can be found into Appendix B where the checklist for the experiment is attached.

4.2.3 Results

The preference score between mix A and B is indicated in percentages. A and B percentages are complementary. One can observe that fact in Figures 4.7 and 4.9, where the preference rating percentage is just given for the first mix A (since the percentage for the second mix B is complementary and deductible).

4.2.3.1 Statistical analysis

The chi-square test with Bonferroni correction is used to determine which of the two mixing pre-sets of the pair is preferred. Chi-square test is applied on the preference rating. In the null hypothesis, scores are the same for both conditions (50%-50%). If a

significant chi-square test result is obtained means that our preference rating is unlikely to be 50%-50%; therefore, there is a significant preference for one of the mixings.

The chi-square test with Bonferroni correction is used to determine if the mixing preferences change due to the multitrack source (original or estimated). Chi-square test is applied as a goodness of fit test. The null hypothesis is set to be the preference distributions for the *Standard* vs. *mixMT*. The test consists on measuring how the preference distribution for the *Standard* vs. *mixSS* fits the null hypothesis. A significant result means that the distributions differ and the mixing preferences change due to the SS algorithm.

4.2.3.2 Popular music

The popular music study is designed to answer the previously posed research question: Do CI users perceive the error/artifacts produced by the non-perfect estimation of the multitrack? (using state of the art SS techniques over popular music). It is important to keep the research question in mind to understand properly the results.

With pairs *-6dBSS* vs. *-6dBMT* and *-12dBSS* vs. *-12dBMT* one would observe directly if there are perceptual differences (a preference) due to the SS algorithm.

But when comparing conditions *-6dBSS* vs. *Standard* w.r.t. *-6dBMT* vs. *Standard*, and *-12dBSS* vs. *Standard* w.r.t. *-12dBMT* vs. *Standard*, one would observe if the mixing preferences change due to the different multitrack source.

In Table 4.9 the results are given averaging for CI subjects and NH subjects (further summarized in Figure 4.7).

	CI ratings	χ^2 test p-value	NH ratings	χ^2 test p-value
-6dBSS vs. -6dBMT	46.92%-53.08%	.4321	32.10%-67.90%	5.191e-06
-12dBSS vs. -12dBMT	40.12%-59.88%	.0119	24.08%-75.92%	4.121e-11
-6dBSS vs. Standard	54.32%-45.68%	.2714	25.92%-74.08%	8.885e-10
-6dBMT vs. Standard	52.47%-47.53%	.5297	29.02%-70.98%	9.163e-08
-12dBSS vs. Standard	42.60%-57.40%	.0593	8.03%-91.97%	< 2.2e-16
-12dBMT vs. Standard	52.47%-47.53%	.5297	12.96%-87.04%	< 2.2e-16

TABLE 4.9: *Experiment 2 results for the popular music study. Significant results are highlighted in bold ($\alpha = 0.05$).*

FIGURE 4.7: *Experiment 2 results for the popular music study. Preference rating percentages are just given for the first mix (since the percentage for the second mix is complementary and deductible).*

NH subjects significantly prefer a MT source rather than a SS estimated, showing up that NH perceive the artifacts coming from the SS algorithm. Furthermore, NH also significantly prefer the *Standard* mixing condition rather than any other proposed.

Regarding CI subjects results, they show a significant preference for *-12dBMT* condition rather than *-12dBSS*, showing that they can perceive the SS artifacts/errors of the vocals when the background is enough (12dB) attenuated. But it is important here to highlight that when the background is attenuated 6dB, CI subjects can not perceive the artifacts/errors coming from the SS (since there is no significant preference for *-6dBMT* or *-6dBSS*).

Finally, we can observe how CI subjects mixing preferences change when changing the multitrack source:

- No significant preference was found for *-6dBSS* or *Standard* conditions nor for *-6dBMT* or *Standard* conditions. Their preference distributions do not differ (χ^2 goodness of fit test: p-value = 0.6369).
- No significant preference was found for *-12dBSS* or *Standard* conditions nor for *-12dBMT* or *Standard* conditions. But their preference distributions differ significantly (χ^2 goodness of fit test: p-value = 0.011), showing that the artifacts are perceivable when attenuating the background 12dB.

Previously presented results do not require Bonferroni correction because it is a planned comparison over pre-defined pairs. It is not an study trying to find out every possible

comparison in a post-hoc analysis. There is no temptation to do more comparisons after looking the data since the experiment was previously designed in that way.

Individual results for each subject can be found in Table 4.13; where one can observe contradictory mixing preferences between different CI subjects. For example: S8 significantly prefer the *Standard* condition over all others but S10 significantly prefer *-6dB* and *-12dB* conditions over *Standard*.

Finally, individual results also show that only S10 showed a significant preference for the *-12dBMT* condition over the *-12dBSS*. Showing that even globally the results express a significant preference for the *-12dBMT* condition over the *-12dBSS*, for most CI subjects attenuating the background 12dB is still not enough to perceive the artifacts/errors present into the vocals due to the SS.

Estimating a benchmark for SS algorithms

It is also interesting to find some theoretical estimations from the experimental data. The preference rating for the SS vs. MT and the objective measures (SDR, SIR, SAR) are known. In Figure 4.8 are faced to estimate a theoretical boundary that defines what a *good* multitrack estimation is (in a sense that CI users do not perceive the artifacts).

The objective measures are related to the voice source, since for the *-6dB* and *-12dB* mixings the voice level is the most prominent. When re-mixing after attenuating the background sources, the errors/artifacts perceivable are from the voice source.

One can note that in Figure 4.8 ratings never exceed the non-significant upper bound (70.37%), since this would mean that there is a significant preference for the estimated multitrack over the original; however, exceeding the lower bound means that the original multitrack is preferred over the estimated. The percentage interval highlighted in green (from 29.63% to 70.37%) corresponds to the ratings having a p-value > 0.05 of a chi-square test result (with H_0 : equal preference for both conditions, 50%-50%.) given that 27 samples are gathered along the experiments (3 repetitions x 9 CI subjects = 27).

Higher values of the objective measures (SDR, SIR and SAR) represent a better separation quality. Therefore, one would expect a positive correlation between the preference for the SS mix and the SDR, SIR and SAR values (see Table 4.10). One can observe that the SIR values are negatively correlated *w.r.t.* the SS preference ratings; showing that (for the *-6dB* and *-12dB* mixings) the interferences from other sources do not influence

subjects judgment (because when improving SIR, the separation is always better). This happens because we are mixing two estimated tracks: the interferences coming from other sources are mutually combined and are not perceivable. Therefore, SIR values are not relevant.

The gathered data is shaped using two models: linear regression and measuring the minimum SDR/SAR value inside the non-preference area.

The former model is rather weak since only 6 songs (in Table 4.6) are measured. The intersection between the linear regression (dark line in Figure 1) and the lower vertical line (light line) in Figure 4.8 gives the minimum recommended SDR/SAR values from where CI recipients start perceiving the estimated multitrack as it was the original multitrack (no preference): 4.9084/4.9541 (for the -6dB mix) and 5.7366/5.8212 (for the -12dB mix).

The latter is a less restrictive model provided to fix a lower bound value that a SS algorithm may never exceed. It is based on measuring the minimum SDR/SAR inside the non-preference area. For both mixings, -6dB and -12dB, the SDR/SAR values are the same: 3.6692/3.6753; because those values correspond to the same song (see Figure 4.8).

This way of interpreting the data is interesting to quantify from which levels of SDR/SAR CI users are starting not to perceive the artifacts: a useful benchmark to check before using a SS technique.

	Mixing	Corr. coeff.
SDR	-6dB	0.3857
	-12dB	0.3585
SIR	-6dB	-0.2896
	-12dB	-0.2275
SAR	-6dB	0.4087
	-12dB	0.3802

TABLE 4.10: “Corr. coeff.” refers to the correlation between the SS ratings and each of the objective measures scores.

FIGURE 4.8: Results facing the objective measures (*SDR*, *SIR* and *SAR*, in rows) with the preference ratings for the first condition considering two different mixings: -6dB and -12dB (first and second columns, respectively). Third column depicts a comparison between the -6dB and the -12dB linear regression models. Songs are represented as points. The green highlighted zone (from 29.63% to 70.37%) corresponds to the ratings having a p -value > 0.05 of a chi-square test (with H_0 : equal preference for both conditions, 50%-50%.)

Discussion

Errors caused by the SS algorithm can not be perceived for CI users when the background is attenuated by 6dB. But when attenuating the background by 12dB, the estimation errors start to be noticeable. In general we observed that CI users can perceive the difference when attenuating the background 12dB, but when checking the results individually one realizes that not all users can perceive it.

We could also observe that even using the estimated multitrack, CIs mixing preferences do not change when attenuating the background by 6dB. But when attenuating by 12dB, the SS errors begin to be noticeable and the mixing preferences change: subjects show a preference trend for *Standard* rather than -12dBSS condition.

Therefore: if the mixing pre-sets do not attenuate more than 6dB the background instruments, SS techniques obtaining SDR and SAR values for the singing voice source above

4.9084 and 4.9541 are recommended. However, if the SDR and SAR values are above 3.6692 and 3.6753 for most CI users would be already enough. This is a noticeable result because it means that simplifying the music by means of re-mixing is a feasible approach since most of the commercial songs are mono or stereo (and require a pre-processing step to estimate the multitrack before re-mixing).

Another interesting result, that the literature do not cover, is the individual mixing preferences. General mixing pre-sets solutions may not be helpful for everyone. Individual subject-specific mixing pre-sets are the unique way to exploit the potential of this approach. Technologies like SS, that allow individual configurations, seem to be a promising approach towards a better music appreciation for CI users.

4.2.3.3 Orchestral music

The orchestral music study is designed to answer the previously posed research question: do CI users enjoy better orchestral music given a different mixing setup than NH listeners? We will answer this question analyzing if there is any significant preference for *Standard* or for any of the mixing pre-sets proposed after Experiment 1.

In Table 4.11 (further summarized in Figure 4.9) one can observe that NH subjects significantly prefer the *Standard* mixing pre-set and CI subjects do not show any significant preference for any specific mixing pre-set.

	CI ratings	χ^2 test p-value	NH ratings	χ^2 test p-value
-6dB vs. Standard	46.91%-53.09%	.4321	10.50%-89.50%	< 2.2e-16
Details vs. Standard	51.23%-48.77%	.7533	20.37%-79.63%	4.611e-14
Beat6 vs. Standard	41.35%-58.65%	.0278	22.22%-77.78%	1.537e-12
Beat12 vs. Standard	53.08%-46.92%	.4321	17.90%-82.10%	3.058e-16
-12dB vs. Standard	53.70%-46.30%	.3458	6.18%-93.82%	< 2.2e-16

TABLE 4.11: *Experiment 2 results for the orchestral music study. Significant results are highlighted in bold (with Bonferroni correction; $m = 5$, $\alpha = 0.01$).*

But during Experiment 1 differences between users having different levels of classical music training were found. Table 4.12 and Figure 4.10 show the percentage ratings when dividing the population into two groups: trained/NOT trained; with 2 and 7 subjects respectively. There, one can observe a significant preference for the *Details* condition over the *Standard* for trained subjects.

FIGURE 4.9: *Experiment 2 results for the orchestral music study. Preference rating percentages are just given for the first mix (since the percentage for the second mix is complementary and deductible).*

	CI trained ratings	χ^2 test p-value	CI NOT trained ratings	χ^2 test p-value
-6dB vs. Standard	38.89%-61.11%	.1824	49.20%-50.80%	.8586
Details vs. Standard	77.78%-22.22%	.0008	48.41%-51.59%	.7216
Beat6 vs. Standard	27.78%-72.22%	.0076	44.44%-55.56%	.2123
Beat12 vs. Standard	69.44%-30.56%	.0196	51.59%-48.42%	.7216
-12dB vs. Standard	47.22%-52.78%	.7389	54.76%-45.24%	.2850

TABLE 4.12: *Experiment 2 results for the orchestral music study dividing the population into two groups: trained/NOT trained. Significant results are highlighted in bold (with Bonferroni correction; $m = 10$, $\alpha = 0.005$).*

FIGURE 4.10: *Experiment 2 results for the orchestral music study dividing the population into two groups: trained/NOT trained. Preference rating percentages are just given for the first mix (since the percentage for the second mix is complementary and deductible).*

Subject	Residual Hearing (Plugged)	Pop music experience	-6dBSS vs.		-12dBSS vs.		-6dBMT vs.		-12dBSS vs.		-12dBMT vs.	
			-6dBMT	Standard	-12dBMT	Standard	-6dBMT	Standard	-12dBSS	Standard	-12dBMT	Standard
BSS009-S6	YES	NO	50%-50%	72.22%-27.78%	27.78%-72.22%	66.67%-33.33%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	0%-100%	100%-0%
BSS010-S7	YES	NO	38.89%-61.11%	66.67%-33.33%	55.56%-44.44%	88.89% -11.11%	77.78%-22.22%	77.78%-22.22%	77.78%-22.22%	77.78%-22.22%	0%-100%	100%-0%
BSS011-S8	NO	YES	38.89%-61.11%	11.11%-88.89%	44.44%-55.56%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%
BSS012-S1	NO	NO	77.78%-22.22%	72.22%-27.78%	33.33%-66.67%	94.44% -5.56%	72.22%-27.78%	72.22%-27.78%	72.22%-27.78%	72.22%-27.78%	100%-0%	100%-0%
BSS013-S9	NO	YES	27.78%-72.22%	77.78%-22.22%	44.44%-55.56%	38.89%-61.11%	22.22%-77.78%	22.22%-77.78%	22.22%-77.78%	22.22%-77.78%	44.44%-55.56%	44.44%-55.56%
BSS014-S10	NO	YES	50%-50%	16.67%-83.33%	16.67%-83.33%	88.89% -11.11%	94.44% -5.56%	94.44% -5.56%	94.44% -5.56%	94.44% -5.56%	0%-100%	0%-100%
BSS020-S3	NO	YES	50%-50%	44.44%-55.56%	44.44%-55.56%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%	0%-100%
BSS021-S11	NO	NO	44.44%-55.56%	38.89%-61.11%	50%-50%	27.78%-72.22%	5.56%-94.44%	5.56%-94.44%	5.56%-94.44%	5.56%-94.44%	22.22%-77.78%	22.22%-77.78%
BSS023-S12	NO	YES	44.44%-55.56%	55.56%-44.44%	44.44%-55.56%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	50%-50%	50%-50%

TABLE 4.13: *Experiment 2 individual results: popular music. Significant results are highlighted in bold (with Bonferroni correction; $m = 9$, $\alpha = 0.0055$).*

Subject	Residual Hearing (Plugged)	Classical music experience	-6dB vs.		Details vs.		Beat6 vs.		Beat12 vs.		-12dB vs.	
			Standard									
BSS009-S6	YES	NO	72.22%-27.78%	55.56%-44.44%	55.56%-44.44%	50%-50%	50%-50%	50%-50%	50%-50%	38.89%-61.11%	38.89%-61.11%	38.89%-61.11%
BSS010-S7	YES	YES	66.67%-33.33%	66.67%-33.33%	66.67%-33.33%	44.44%-55.56%	44.44%-55.56%	50%-50%	50%-50%	83.33% -16.67%	83.33% -16.67%	83.33% -16.67%
BSS011-S8	NO	NO	16.67%-83.33%	66.67%-33.33%	66.67%-33.33%	38.89%-61.11%	38.89%-61.11%	66.67%-33.33%	66.67%-33.33%	38.89%-61.11%	38.89%-61.11%	38.89%-61.11%
BSS012-S1	NO	YES	11.11%-88.89%	55.56%-44.44%	55.56%-44.44%	16.67%-83.33%	16.67%-83.33%	66.67%-33.33%	66.67%-33.33%	16.67%-83.33%	16.67%-83.33%	16.67%-83.33%
BSS013-S9	NO	NO	44.44%-55.56%	27.78%-72.22%	27.78%-72.22%	55.56%-44.44%	55.56%-44.44%	33.33%-66.67%	33.33%-66.67%	50%-50%	50%-50%	50%-50%
BSS014-S10	NO	NO	50%-50%	50%-50%	50%-50%	38.89%-61.11%	38.89%-61.11%	44.44%-55.56%	44.44%-55.56%	77.78% -22.22%	77.78% -22.22%	77.78% -22.22%
BSS020-S3	NO	NO	50%-50%	50%-50%	50%-50%	38.89%-61.11%	38.89%-61.11%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	72.22%-27.78%	72.22%-27.78%	72.22%-27.78%
BSS021-S11	NO	NO	61.11%-38.89%	38.89%-61.11%	38.89%-61.11%	44.44%-55.56%	44.44%-55.56%	61.11%-38.89%	61.11%-38.89%	55.56%-44.44%	55.56%-44.44%	55.56%-44.44%
BSS023-S12	NO	NO	50%-50%	50%-50%	50%-50%	44.44%-55.56%	44.44%-55.56%	44.44%-55.56%	44.44%-55.56%	50%-50%	50%-50%	50%-50%

TABLE 4.14: *Experiment 2 individual results: orchestral music. Significant results are highlighted in bold (with Bonferroni correction; $m = 45$, $\alpha = 0.0011$). Highly significant results ($> 75\%$) are highlighted in red bold.*

The individual results for the CI users are attached in Table 4.14, where only one significant (with a strong Bonferroni correction: $m = 45$; $\alpha = 0.0011$) preference was found in S1 (trained in classical music) for the *Standard* condition over the *-6dBMT*. In order to avoid missing important results due to the restrictive Bonferroni correction, highly significant results are **highlighted in red** at Table 4.14 (the 75% threshold is established arbitrarily by the authors). One can observe contradictory mixing preferences between different CI subjects. For example: S7 enjoys more the *-12dB* condition over the *Standard* but S1 enjoys more the *Standard* over the *-12dB*. It is also interesting to see how S1 (in general) prefers the *Standard* condition; note that S1 has classical music training, meaning that this user has developed his own skills to be able to enjoy NH orchestral music mixings.

Discussion

Non trained CI users have difficulties to perceive the details of classical music. This is concluded from the fact that no mixing preferences were found in this group, probably due to the lack of music understanding. Since they are not used (trained) to listen classical music, typically more complex and less enjoyable [Gfeller et al., 2010; Looi et al., 2007], they are probably not able to distinguish the musical objects such as instruments or sections. This finding agrees with the literature, that suggests listening to music regularly to improve the level of enjoyment [Gfeller et al., 2003]. Moreover, this lack of music understanding can be related to the fact that a big amount of instruments are involved in an orchestral music piece (increasing complexity). One can note that the proposed mixings are only attenuated by a maximum of 12 dB, which is probably not enough to be perceived by untrained CI subjects in a scenario with so many instruments. Increasing the attenuations, for example from 12 dB to 24 dB, could be a way to make the differences more obvious for untrained CI subjects.

Trained subjects, however, showed a significant preference for the *Details* mixing pre-set. This result confirms the observations from Experiment 1, where it was shown that trained subjects prefer to enforce musicological details rather than the beat. This mixing enforces musicological details that CIs do not encode well (*i.e.* secondary melodies) and attenuates the percussion section that is usually well encoded with CIs.

But, similar to the pop study, trained CI users would not benefit from general mixing pre-sets solutions. Individual subject-specific mixing pre-sets are the unique way to

exploit the potential of re-mixing the music.

Therefore, in our experiments we could observe that modifying the relative instrument level settings potentially improves orchestral music enjoyment for trained CI users; showing a preference for the *Details* mixing pre-set.

Chapter 5

Conclusions and future work

This chapter concludes this master thesis. Relates the data gathered during the perceptual tests and the source separation experiments. Main conclusions and observations are described here.

5.1 Popular music

5.1.1 Conclusions

Music simplification by means of re-mixing potentially improves popular music enjoyment for CI users. They prefer the instruments level set significantly lower than the vocals level (attenuating the instruments to favor vocals) and they show a preference for mixings with a more attenuated harmonic part (P/G) (favoring beat and vocals). Those findings agrees with [Buyens et al. \[2014\]](#).

We also found that individual subject-specific mixing pre-sets are the unique way to exploit the potential of this approach. General mixing pre-sets may not be helpful for everyone. Technologies like SS, that allow individual configurations, seem to be the right approach towards a better music appreciation.

We could see that SS techniques can be used for estimating the multitrack recording to be used for this concrete CIs application. Approximately, it is recommended to use SS algorithms that achieve an average SDR and SAR values greater than 4.9084 and 4.9541; however, the minimum SDR and SAR values desirable should be 3.6692 and

3.6753. Those are the lower boundaries estimated that determine when CI users would not perceive such errors in the vocals when attenuating the instruments 6dB. But when attenuating the instruments 12dB, the SS errors begin to be noticeable for CI users. The minimum recommended values of SDR and SAR for the -12dB mix are: 5.7306 and 5.8212, respectively. However, the minimum SDR and SAR values desirable should be 3.6692 and 3.6753.

-	Target (vocals)			Other (background)			Time
	SDR	SIR	SAR	SDR	SIR	SAR	
FASST	5.9914	26.6353	6.1211	9.9288	11.6723	15.4332	4h 39m
DRNN best init.	5.5741	8.4182	10.6996	5.5367	8.7082	10.0786	1m 49s
DRNN baseline	5.5158	8.3022	10.5574	5.5856	9.0515	9.5947	2m 58s
-6dB boundary	4.9084	-	4.9541	-	-	-	-
-12dB boundary	5.7306	-	5.8212	-	-	-	-
Min. desirable	3.6692	-	3.6753	-	-	-	-

TABLE 5.1: Comparing several SS techniques with respect to the theoretical boundaries for different mixings (-6dB and -12dB) from where CI users do not perceive the artifacts.

In Table 5.1 one can observe how DRNN is a competitive model since similar performance is achieved reducing drastically the long run time of FASST. One can observe how FASST outperforms DRNN for SIR measures; but this is not relevant since (in Chapter 4.2) we realized that SIR values are not relevant for bench-marking this application. Therefore, DRNN can be used for estimating the multitrack recordings. Specially when the -6dB mix is used, because its scores are above the -6dB boundary.

It is important here to highlight that the use of DRNN for SS is rather new. Hopefully the state-of-the-art would advance during the following years and future improvements would allow us to use DRNN without compromising at all the separation results.

Source Separation: DRNN initialization study

The baseline DRNN (with Glorot and Bengio [2010] initialization scheme) and the DRNN model with the best initialization (with He et al. [2015] initialization scheme) perform similarly. If the initialization allows the output activations to be inside the data range, the model is able to find a local minimum with similar generalization properties.

Another interesting observation was to see (using the IRNN scheme as a memory proxy) how the temporal dependencies exist, because better performance is achieved using DRNN than DNN, but they are rather sort. That could be the reason why our models, that consider neighbouring frames, do not suffer the inherent problems of DRNN nets

(gradient vanish/explode), because long-term memory is not needed. This denotes the importance of using an input vector with a context window for music models.

5.1.2 Future work

After assessing that SS techniques are suitable for remixing popular music for CI recipients, would be interesting to do a pilot software to assess this technology in a less controlled environment. This software should be able to:

1. Estimate the multitrack recording from a mono or a stereo music piece using SS techniques.
2. Propose several mixing pre-sets so that the user can choose the most appropriate for his own taste.

Such software would be beneficial for CI recipients starting to listen music. Providing music that is *easier* to enjoy would encourage them to keep practicing listening to music.

5.2 Orchestral music

5.2.1 Conclusions

If CI subjects are divided in two groups of expertise: patients with low classical music knowledge prefer a higher percussion section level than the main melody (showing a significant preference for beat, easier to perceive), while patients with a higher level of knowledge show a preference for higher accompaniment levels and attenuated percussion (showing more interest for musicological details than beat, already well encoded).

We could observe how modifying the relative instrument level settings potentially improves orchestral music enjoyment for trained CI users; showing a preference for the *Details* mixing pre-set.

Similarly as in the pop study, trained CI users would not benefit from general mixing pre-sets solutions. Individual subject-specific mixing pre-sets are the unique way to exploit the potential of this approach.

5.2.2 Future work

The first steps towards understanding how to make orchestral music more enjoyable for CI recipients are done. We realized that dividing the instruments of an orchestral song in main melody, percussion and others (similarly as is done into popular music) is not the most appropriate way for doing so. What it actually matters is which music objects are well encoded (or not) in order to enforce (or remove) them. For example, in popular music the sections well encoded are: vocals and bass/drums (beat); and the bad encoded: piano/guitar. Into orchestral music, the better encoded music object is the beat; and the worst encoded are the main melody and secondary melodies. We have observed that the most appropriate way to divide the instruments of an orchestral song is: main melody, beat inducers and others. For trying to define *what is the beat*, would be interesting to find a metric quantifying how much beat each track has (*i.e.* the danceability descriptor [Streich and Herrera, 2005]) in order to choose *objectively* which tracks are responsible of inducing beat.

After learning which is the most appropriate way of dividing the instruments of the orchestral music, would be interesting to repeat Experiment 1 with such division of instruments. Probably the resulting mixing presets would be much more appropriate than the proposed during this first attempt. I would also recommend to restrict a little bit more the searching space of the mixing console in Experiment 1 (restricting the dynamic range of the sliders). Thus, would allow subjects to go faster and to obtain results with less variance, giving results with more statistical power in Experiment 1.

Experiment 2 may be repeated considering the mixing pre-sets gathered in Experiment 1. I would like also advice to do more *exaggerated* mixings. Strong attenuations (*i.e.* 24dB) may be useful for untrained CI users, because otherwise they can not find substantial differences between mixings and they can not benefit from the here proposed approach.

Appendix A

Checklist Experiment 1

BEFORE PATIENT ARRIVES:

- Set the Patient ID and Name into the software.
- Calibrate the system:
 - Set random values to 0.
 - Check with the sonometer that the value that can emit the loudspeaker at -30dB of the slider is 60dBSPL (supposed comfort level).

AFTER PATIENT ARRIVES:

- Be careful on NOT explaining TOO MANY things.
- Introduce Experiment 1 without volume; doing that, the implantee only listens to the researcher instructions. Demonstrate how to manipulate: main control, move slider, save and show them the messages that usually appear.
- Explain that the things are random.
- Advice the CI that the comfort level is adjusted to be around the -30dB position of the sliders, increasing a lot can be too loud.
- **DEMO**

- Prepare CI user:
 - Remove one CI, to avoid variability.
 - Set the common speech mapping.
 - Calibrate the CI device so that at -30dB of the slider corresponds to the comfortable loudness level. DISABLE RANDOM!
 - ENABLE AGAIN RANDOMNESS TO -15dB! (dynamic range -70 to 0)
- The subject is asked to determine the most enjoyable audio mix given the separated audios and a mixing console.
- It is suggested to listen to each mix channel separately before starting the experiment.
- Explain that the user is going to first TRAIN and then TEST.
- **TRAIN** The subject is allowed to have ten trial runs (where all the different songs are present) to learn the system.
- Initial questionnaire:
 - Level of knowledge about classical music? From 1-10.
 - Level of knowledge about popular modern music? From 1-10.
- Ask to the user to be consistent and concentrated along the experiments.
- **START TEST**
- Talk/ask to the subject to gather his opinion and feelings. Which strategy did you followed?

Appendix B

Checklist Experiment 2

BEFORE PATIENT ARRIVES:

- Calibrate the system:
 - Check with the sonometer that the volume is set to 60dB SPL for training part (supposed comfort level).

AFTER PATIENT ARRIVES:

- Be careful on NOT explaining TOO MANY things. Just explain: different mixes are going to be presented. Choose the most enjoyable.
- In order to let them understand the task, Experiment1 is shown.
- Prepare CI user:
 - Remove one CI, to avoid variability.
 - Set the common speech mapping.
 - Calibrate the CI device so that the volume corresponds to the comfortable loudness level.
- **TRAIN**
 - Just explain: different mixes are going to be presented. Choose the most enjoyable. There are no good/bad answers. Each user has its own taste. There are songs where the differences are hard to perceive, choose by details.

- **START TEST**
- Talk/ask to the subject to gather his opinion and feelings. Do you usually listen to music? To popular music? To classical music?

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